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Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
LIST OF FIGURES	6
LIST OF TABLES	6
ABBREVIATIONS	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 THE VITALISE PROJECT	8
1.2 DESCRIPTION OF WP2	8
1.3 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT	8
1.4 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE	8
2 METHODOLOGY	10
2.1 FIRST VERSION OF EVALUATION PROCESS AND TOOLS - HARMONIZATION FRAMEWORK	10
2.2 STATE OF THE ART OF LIVING LAB EXISTING PROCESSES AND SERVICES	16
2.2.1 <i>Gathering comments on definitions</i>	18
2.2.2 <i>Workshop for evaluation process</i>	21
2.2.3 <i>Harmonization Workshop</i>	21
2.2.4 <i>VITALISE Living Lab Interviews</i>	22
2.2.5 <i>Online Engagement of the Living Lab Community Workshop</i>	22
3 RESULTS FROM STATE OF THE ART ANALYSIS	23
3.1 OVERVIEW OF INITIAL RESULTS	23
3.2 USE CASES AND POTENTIAL END-USERS	24
3.3 DATA COLLECTION DEVICES, TECHNOLOGIES AND DATA TYPES	24
3.4 METHODS, TOOLS AND SERVICES	27
4 STANDARD VERSION 0.1	33
4.1 INTRODUCTION	33
4.2 SCOPE OF THIS DOCUMENT	35
4.3 PART 2. LIVING LAB BUSINESS MODEL (LLBM)	35
4.3.1 <i>Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs</i>	35
4.4 PART 5. R&D SERVICES	37
4.4.1 <i>Access to data</i>	38
4.4.2 <i>Intake and matching</i>	38
4.4.3 <i>Capacity building</i>	39
4.4.4 <i>Clinical trials</i>	39
4.4.5 <i>Co-creation session</i>	40
4.4.6 <i>Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking</i>	41
4.4.7 <i>Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study</i>	41
4.4.8 <i>Equipment and facility rental service</i>	42
4.4.9 <i>Expert opinion, and advisory services</i>	42
4.4.10 <i>Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)</i>	43
4.4.11 <i>Temporary research funding</i>	43
4.4.12 <i>Grant writing and funding application support service</i>	43
4.4.13 <i>Idea selection and testing</i>	44
4.4.14 <i>Impact assessment and validation test</i>	44
4.4.15 <i>Innovation network orchestration</i>	45
4.4.16 <i>Large-scale real-life testing and piloting</i>	45
4.4.17 <i>Legal, regulation and safety standard support</i>	45
4.4.18 <i>Living lab project planning and management</i>	46
4.4.19 <i>Marketing and sales support</i>	46
4.4.20 <i>Panel management</i>	46
4.4.21 <i>Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing</i>	47
4.4.22 <i>Prototyping test</i>	47
4.4.23 <i>Public procurement support services</i>	48

4.4.24 *Simulation test* 48

4.4.25 *Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation* 48

4.4.26 *Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping* 49

4.4.27 *Usability testing* 49

4.5 PART 7B. DEVICES AND TECHNOLOGIES 50

5 CONCLUSION **60**

6 REFERENCES **61**

7 ANNEXES **62**

7.1 ANNEX 1 62

List of Figures

FIGURE 1 HARMONIZATION FRAMEWORK 11

FIGURE 2 CONCEPTUAL MATRIX BY SANTONEN TO ILLUSTRATE THE INTERLINKAGE BETWEEN THE KEY DIMENSIONS OF LIVING LABS 20

FIGURE 3 THE KEY ELEMENTS AND CONCEPTUAL OVERVIEW OF THE LIVING LAB MANAGEMENT SYSTEM 33

List of Tables

TABLE 1 DESCRIPTION OF PDCA/PDCA CYCLE METHOD 10

TABLE 2 CONSENSUS LEVEL INTERPRETATION DURING THE VITALISE LIVING LAB HARMONIZATION DECISION MAKING 13

TABLE 3 THE SUMMARY DESCRIPTION OF THE KEY ACTIVITIES AND OUTCOMES OF FIRST STATE OF THE ART PHASE 16

TABLE 4 DATA COLLECTION SUBCATEGORIES 26

TABLE 5 CONSENSUS LEVELS AMONG VITALISE LIVING LABS (N=9) 28

TABLE 6 METHODS, TOOLS AND SERVICES POPULARITY AMONG VITALISE LIVING LABS (N=11) .. 29

TABLE 7 NEW LIVING LAB METHOD, TOOL AND SERVICE SUGGESTION 29

TABLE 9 RESEARCHERS EXPERTISE 35

TABLE 10 DEVICES AND TECHNOLOGIES PROVIDED BY LIVING LABS 50

Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab

Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industry researchers. Towards this end, VITALISE aims to create the first Harmonization guidelines for Living Labs that will facilitate the access of researchers to the provided infrastructures.

This document presents the work performed for the Harmonization of the way Living Labs work for the first semester of VITALISE. The initial work of Harmonization aims to establish the state-of –the-art for the Living Lab services, methods and tools that will be used. This is also used as a baseline upon which the Standard versions will continue evolving throughout VITALISE and beyond. Another important aspect presented in this deliverable is the methodological framework that will be followed in the Harmonization process.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Some of the main tasks is the establishment of the harmonization procedures within the consortium and beyond, the management and organization of the Harmonization procedure events (Harmonization Body and Board meetings) and the definition and update of the Standards and Key Performance Indicators by identifying and documenting the existing Living Lab processes, and the similarities and differences among the consortium’s Living Lab partners.

VITALISE Harmonization Body is a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to co-ordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and is consisted of representatives of each Living Lab in the consortium as well as independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

1.3 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present the first version of the methodological framework that will be followed during the Harmonization and will also be updated and presented in D2.2. Also, this document presents all the data collection and analysis that is being done during these first months of implementation. Although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 1”, the authors of this deliverable decided that the specific standard should be Version 0.1 as it is not yet including all the required parts to reach Version 1.0. This document does not constitute the Standard Version 0.1 of the Living Labs services, methods and tools but a more elaborate version. The aggregated results will be structured in a comprehensive way and will create Standard Version 0.1.

1.4 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** outlines the proposed methodological framework for the Harmonization procedure but also presents the already performed activities for the Harmonization
- **Section 3** discusses the results, limitations and current open issues that came out from the work performed in the collection of the state of the art for Living Labs.
- **Section 4** includes all the information that will constitute the Standard Version 0.1. This Section also summarizes the scope of the Harmonization and the draft format for the rest Standard Versions of VITALISE.
- **Section 5** provides some concluded remarks for this deliverable

2 Methodology

2.1 First version of evaluation process and tools - Harmonization Framework

The VITALISE proposed methodology for Harmonisation is based on a modified version of the PDCA/PDSA methodology, combined with principles and ideas of the Agile development cycle. This is a preliminary, draft version of the methodology that will be further improved and reported in the D2.2 Evaluation process and tools. The VITALISE proposed methodology begins with a linear phase aiming to summarize the commonalities of the Living Labs procedures and services as a first standard (pre-study phase). The following iterations of harmonization methodology will be progressively attempting to harmonize procedures and services that are similar (but not identical) in the living labs, allowing for a 6-month testing and studying of the new harmonized procedures, before accepting or rejecting.

The PDCA/PDSA (plan–do–check–act, plan–do–study–act) method is widely accepted in healthcare and therefore, identified as a suitable quality management system for living lab harmonization process. In Table 1, Deming’s original PDCA model (1986), Langley’s adaptation to healthcare (1996) and Speroff and O’Connor’s adaptation to scientific methodology (2004) are presented as described by Taylor et al. (2014).

Table 1 Description of PDCA/PDSA cycle method

PDCA/PDSA cycle phase	Deming’s (1986) original model in manufacturing	Langely’s (1996) adaption in healthcare context	Speroff and O’Connor’s analogue to scientific methodology (2004)
Plan	Plan a change or test aimed at improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify objective Identify questions and predictions Plan to carry out the cycle (what, who, when, where) 	Formation of a hypothesis for improvement
Do	Carry out the change or test (preferably on a small scale)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Execute the plan Document problems and unexpected observations Begin data analysis 	Conduct study protocol with collection of data
Check/Study	Examine the results. What did we learn? What went wrong?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete the data analysis Compare data to predictions Summarise what was learnt 	Analysis and interpretation of the results
Act	Adopt the change, abandon it or run through cycle again	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What changes are to be made? What will the next cycle entail? 	Iteration for what to do next

Moreover, agile development is a process that is nowadays adopted by most of the companies dealing with the development of ICT products. The agile development has shown to improve development performance and when adopted providing more efficient and effective adaptation to changes in user requirements (Lee and Xia, 2010). Although agile principles are focusing on managements for software development, they can be easily extended to other design and development fields and are nowadays adopted by a variety of industries. More specifically, inspired by agile principles, VITALISE harmonization methodology follows the following principles:

- The highest priority is to satisfy the researchers and developers that require efficient and effective access to research infrastructures and services.
- Welcome changes in the standard version at every time of the development.
- Deliver standards in a practical, comprehensive way frequently (every 6 months)

- Communication among the Harmonization Board and Body should be continuous and frequent.
- At regular intervals, the Harmonization team will reflect on the methodology in order to exchange knowledge and become more effective.

VITALISE leveraging on the concept of Design Thinking, which starts from an existing problem to be explored, setting the current status of the Living Labs, similar to what is done in the Design Thinking phase. The iterative process of VITALISE is based on the PDCA/PDSA. Each iteration will take place every 6 months and the outcome will be a new Standard Version deliverable (D2.1, D2.3-D2.7).

In the picture below the methodology of the VITALISE harmonization process is depicted. The first linear (State of the art) phase is the one performed in Task 2.1. Every iteration presented in the cycle will take place every 6 months and the outcome will be the deliverable of the Standard Version (D2.3-D2.7). Each step depicted in the methodology (Figure 1) is described in detail below.

Figure 1 Harmonization framework

The first three steps in the linear phase (Common Database, Harmonization Body meeting and interviews) were performed in the first 6 months of implementation and are presented in detail in Section 2.2. Here we summarize some basic information about these steps.

Common Database

Explanation/Objective: This is the phase for identifying the current initial status. All living labs participate in data collection by providing data about their state of the art, their services, tools and methods along with their interpretation.

Input: Living labs experience and knowledge

Output/Outcome: A common database including a first set of services, tools and methods

Sample Group: VITALISE consortium partners

Harmonization Body Meeting

Explanation/Objective: It is the first time the harmonization body meets for analyzing the data collected from the Common Database phase.

Input: The common database from the Common Database phase

Output/Outcome: A revised common database

Sample Group: Harmonization Body

Interviews

Explanation/Objective: To gain a deeper understanding of how each Living Lab offers specific services and implements methods.

Input: The revised common database

Output/Outcome: Comments about the implementation of different services

Sample Group: Harmonization Body

Co-Creation

Explanation/Objective: The objective of this step is to explore and identify new procedures that have not been mapped before and do not appear in any of the previous standard versions as well as to identify changes on the existing standard versions that will increase the KPIs. The exploration of new unmapped procedures will be done by studying and analyzing the information provided by the living labs during this phase. The discussion on the existing and “implemented” procedures will be done by taking into account the report with proposed updates for the Living Labs services, procedures and methods (the output of the “Revise and Adjust” phase). It is essential to include a multifaceted group, best if with different skillsets & perspectives, to build on each other’s ideas. Thus, this phase requires the participation of living labs and stakeholders to work together towards eliciting information about emerging but also existing living lab procedures, services and methods.

Input: Discussion during an ideation session (online through tools such as Miro, or physical meeting) where both living labs and stakeholders will be invited. The topic of the discussion will focus on the report with proposed changes for the services, procedures and methods that have gone through the “Implement” phase as well as those that the living labs have not provided yet to their stakeholders

Output/Outcome: An updated Living Labs services, procedures and methods list with the potential addition of unmapped items so far. An initial description for each of the new items will be drafted based on the outputs and outcomes of this step.

Sample Group: Harmonization Body (internal, external living labs and stakeholders)

Events (Implementation steps):

1. Know your stakeholders: For VITALISE, the stakeholders are the researchers and developers in the health and wellbeing domain that need efficient access to research infrastructures. In each cycle the defined group of researchers that will take advantage of Living Lab services will be investigated.

2. Know your services: Gather and study the several services provided by the Living Labs.

3. Know what is being done now: Determine your current status, performance and level of service delivery. This event is performed by studying how the Living Labs provide/deliver the new services and procedures and how many Living Labs provide identical or similar services and procedures.

Tools to be used:

- Tools for the ideation phase of co-creation
- Miro (in case of online), boards and post-its (in case of physical meetings)

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- participation of more than 10 Living Labs
- participation of 20 Stakeholders (researchers, etc.), as identified by the harmonization procedure

Possible Risks: Brining living labs and stakeholders at the same session to have a multifaceted group (cannot take place offline). Manage to integrate all Living Labs into this process in order to be aware of new research and innovations.

Consensus

Explanation/Objective: To come to an agreement about the harmonization process among the members of the body but also among the members of the board (voting). This step aims to resolve any conflicts that came out in the study process. By dictionary definition the term consensus is “a generally accepted opinion or decision among a group of people” (Cambridge Dictionary). However, there is no universally accepted decision rules to define when the consensus has been reached. Common approaches are simple majority and supermajority. A simple majority is reached when 50% of the voters support the decision or opinion whereas common supermajority thresholds are typically 90%, 80%, 75%, 70% or two thirds. In the Table 2 consensus level interpretations during the VITALISE living lab harmonization decision making are presented.

Table 2 Consensus level interpretation during the VITALISE living lab harmonization decision making

Consensus level of the voters	Agreement interpretation	Color code
Over or equal to 80%	Strong supermajority agreement	
Over or equal to 70% but less than 80%	Supermajority agreement	
Over or equal to 50%, but less than 70%	Simple majority agreement	
Over or equal to 30%, but less than 50%	Simple majority disagreement	
Less than 30%	Supermajority disagreement	

The items presented in living lab research infrastructure standard (e.g. a method name and description), should achieve at least supermajority agreement level among VITALISE consortium living labs and Harmonization Body before they can be officially included into the revised and published standard. Items achieving at least simple majority level are considered as “candidates” and are made publicly available as part of standard with “candidate remark” in order to stimulate public debate. All items below 50% agreement will have to go under new development rounds and are considered as working progress items. These items are not included into standard documents. The more detailed decision-making processes among VITALISE consortium living labs and harmonization body are defined in M7, when the first Harmonization Body meeting will take place. The rules for consensus are susceptible to changes during the Revise and adjust phase.

Input: The description and the template that have come out of the Co-creation, as well as the previous Revise and Adjust phase.

Output/Outcome: The level of agreement (consensus) for all the procedures and services that have gone through the implementation phase or the emerging ones that came out from the Co-creation phase.

Sample Group: Harmonization Body or Harmonization Board

Events (Implementation steps):

- Identify conflicts (based on definition)
- Discuss conflicts
- Come to a consensus

Tools to be used:

- common workshop
- four-point Likert scale including strongly disagree, disagree, agree, strongly agree
- eDelphi study
- crowdsourcing – crowdrating (can be used occasionally)

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Consensus from 80% or over of the Harmonization Body/Board = Excellent
- Consensus from 70% but less than 80% of the Harmonization Body = Good
- Consensus from 50% but less than 70% of the Harmonization Body/Board = Poor
- Consensus from less than 50% of the Harmonization Body/Board = Rejected

Possible Risks: Not finding common ground and achieving consensus

Approval Process

Explanation/Objective: To Approve and Publish the current version of the Standard that came out of the Consensus after going through a Public Review event for final comments.

Input: The items with supermajority consensus from the Consensus Phase, or less if Harmonization Body/Board agrees to do so

Output/Outcome: The Standard version for the current iteration.

Sample Group: Harmonization Body or Harmonization Board

Events (Implementation steps):

- Public Review: an event that involves the public in providing their views and feedback on the consensus to consider in decision-making. The items with supermajority consensus, along with all the information and the harmonized data) become publicly accessible for a certain period. The platform that will support the sharing of the proposed Standard allows everyone to provide feedback, comments or even to raise potential objections in an anonymous manner. From VITALISE, the corresponding website section with comments enabled, will be used.
- Approve: The Harmonization Board meets to review the comments and feedback received during the Public Review, making adaptations and approving the current version
- Publish: The final event includes the dissemination of the results of the harmonization process and the Standard version at the official site of the VITALISE project as well as 2 more social media channels

Tools to be used:

- meeting of the Harmonization Board (physical or online)
- websites and mailing lists
- eDelphi study
- Platform with comment enabled functionality for the Public Review event

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Standard available for public review for one week Approved by at least 80% of the Harmonization Board = Excellent
- Approved by at least 80% of the Harmonization Board = Excellent
- Approved by at least 70% but less than 80% of the Harmonization Body = Good
- Approved by at least 50% but less than 70% of the Harmonization Body/Board = Poor
- Approved by at less than 50% of the Harmonization Body/Board = Rejected
- Published on 3 websites (VITALISE, ENoLL, Forum LLSA)
- Disseminate the published version to mailing list and social media

Possible Risks: Risk of losing added value, information that would be important for some and pose problems for others

Implement

Explanation/Objective: Implementation of the research activities from all the Living Labs involved. Living Labs are invited to adopt the current approved and public Standard, focusing more (if possible) on the new services and modifications that the current standard has introduced. To do so, the living labs should be involving the proper stakeholders to use the provided services and procedures. For VITALISE, the stakeholders are the researchers of the JRAs along with the selected researchers for Transnational Access.

Input: The current approved and published Standard

Output/Outcome: The information/feedback collected from the Living Labs after the implementation of the of the research activities

Sample Group: Stakeholders using Living Labs' harmonized services and procedures

Events (Implementation steps):

- Planning by choosing the services that will be deployed in the consortium LL
- Period for implementation
- KPIs and feedback collection from the living labs

Tools to be used: digital platform for reporting KPIs and feedback, (e.g., google forms), self-assessment grid

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Quantitative questionnaire for Standard version (questions about usefulness, usability, presentation, level of applicability, services that are not included)
- Quantitative questionnaire for LL marking
- KPIs for LL status (number of publications, number of new customers, new funding, new collaborations, maintained collaborations/stakeholders etc.)

Possible Risks: Risk that living labs do not recognize themselves in the self-assessment grid and in the score assigned according to their activities

Revise & Adjust

Explanation/Objective: To reflect on the feedback and KPIs collected during the implementation Phase for each of the services and procedures. To understand better what has worked and what has not gone well in order to propose adjustments for the harmonized service or procedure that could lead to better KPIs.

Input: Documents/lists completed from the Living Labs (about the number and description of the existing services, processes, use cases examples, tools etc.) and KPIs from the “Implement” phase

Output/Outcome: A report with proposed updates for the Living Labs services, processes and methods.

Sample Group: Harmonization Body

Events (Implementation steps):

Tools to be used:

- Interviews, mostly with Living Labs to understand what they have done
- Analysis of the KPIs (quantitative and qualitative)
- eDelphi study for external LL

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators):

- Interview at least 70% of LL that participated in the “Implement” phase

Possible Risks: Difficulties in communication/lack of time for performing the interviews, difficulties in reaching common terminology about use cases and provided services/methodologies among the stakeholders (Living Labs).

2.2 State of the art of Living Lab existing processes and services

The activities performed from M1-M6 in the Harmonization process resulted in Standard Version 0.1, presented in this deliverable. The the key activities and outcomes of the state of executed in M1 to M6 are presented in Table 2 and elaborated more in-depth in follow-up sections.

Table 3 The summary description of the key activities and outcomes of first state of the art phase

Steps	Activities during the phase
Objective	An initial mapping and understanding of the state-of-the-art and the terminology used by the stakeholders (Living Labs)
Questions and predictions	<p>RQ1. Who are the key research users and user cases in living lab research infrastructure?</p> <p>RQ2. What are the main data collection technologies in health and wellbeing living lab research?</p> <p>RQ3. What are the main methods, tools and (validated) scientific instruments utilized in health and wellbeing living lab research?</p>

Plan to carry out the cycle (what, who, when, where)	<p>The T2.1 task leader (LAUREA) and VITALISE coordinators execute and manage the data collection, analysis and reporting process.</p> <p>All VITALISE living labs participated in data collection by providing data about the current status of their living lab. Furthermore, 2 public events were carried out, one interactive webinar and one workshop during the Digital Living Lab Days to engage living lab community beyond VITALISE-project. The main activities included the following.</p> <p>M2 The process of identifying current initial status regarding RQ1 to RQ3 as presented in Appendix 1.</p> <p>M2: Analysis of the 1st data collection phase</p> <p>M3: Open interactive webinar with VITALISE-project</p> <p>M4-6: VITALISE Living lab interviews</p> <p>M6: Online workshop in Digital Living Lab Days (open access for DLLD participants) as presented in Appendix 1.</p> <p>M6: Analysis of the 2nd data collection phase results</p> <p>M6: Writing and finalizing deliverable</p>
General Observations:	<p>Plans were executed almost as planned. A few new tasks were identified and partially launched based on emerged needs during data collection process. New task included (1) producing a lexicon and define the key term relating living lab RI and (2) identify validated scientific instruments for living lab data collection activities including such as Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), patient-reported experience measures (PREMs) and other similar instruments commonly used in health and wellbeing research.</p>
Problems/ Challenges:	<p>Due resource intensive multiple parallel tasks (especially JRAs: WP5, WP6, WP7) and holiday seasons, responses from some of the VITALISE partners were at times a bit delayed, which caused time pressure for those managing the T2.1 process. In-depth interviews had also to be limited to cover only RQ1 to RQ3, since the amount of time to cover all the question was not possible in the given time frame. These RQs will be covered more in-depth in later cycles.</p>
Key findings and comparison to predictions	<p>RQ1. The key research users and user cases. In all 21 user types were identified. The user types and uses cases are described in Annex 1.</p> <p>RQ2. The main data collection technologies. A total of 52 data collection technologies divided in 8 main categories were identified. The technologies and categories are described in PART 7B. Devices and technologies.</p> <p>RQ3. The main methods, tools and (validated) scientific instruments. The level of consensus regarding the titles and descriptions of the services/tools/methods identified by Product Validation in Health project's (ProVaHealth) (Santonen, 2020) resulted the following: (1) 93.8% of the title names were strongly agreed or agreed, and (2) 27.3 % of the descriptions were strongly agreed or agreed and 72.7 % had minor disagreement. Furthermore, 10 new services items were identified, but consensus among them was not evaluated. Each living lab method/tool/service offering was identified as well as the overall distribution among VITALISE living labs. The methods/tools/services are described in PART 5. R&D Services.</p> <p>A total of 59 scientific instruments/scales were identified and described in in Appendix 1. (43 PROMs and PREMs list + 16 Physical functioning list)</p>

The key implications	Inconsistency in the use of terminology made at times difficult to determine the answers for the defined RQs and reach consensus among the VITALISE consortium members. Inconsistency was cross cutting all RQs and therefore a decision was made to produce living lab RI lexicon, which covers all the relevant main terms. Also, terminological hierarchy must be defined to clarify the relationship between service, tool, method, instrument, RQ1. The key research users and user cases.
Did the change lead to improvement? Why or why not?	Since the 1 st cycle focused on evaluating the current status of VITALISE living labs RI no serious attempts were made to implement the standard in operational usage. However, during the Joint Research Actions in WP5 to WP7, the preliminary results are used when defining the research protocols.
What was the starting point?	The 1 st cycle was an initial analysis of the current state in which the VITALISE consortium current status was compared to Product Validation in Health project's (ProVaHealth) results (Santonen, 2020). ProVaHealth was an Interreg Baltic Sea Region funded three years project (October 2017 to March 2020) to co-create sustainable business models and services for living labs and support SMEs and start-ups internationalization efforts. Similar initiatives will be identified and studied in the following Standard Versions.
What will the next cycle entail?	The objectives for the next cycle will be defined in more detail during M7 but will consist e.g. (1) identifying the key terms and producing the lexicon for living lab RI, (2) conducting systematic data collection regarding RQ1 to RQ3 within ENOLL network and among other interested living labs.

The following Sections present information about the separate steps performed in gathering the State of the art towards the creation of the Standard Version 1.

2.2.1 Gathering comments on definitions

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS: During the first data collection phase, the main aim was to gain initial understanding of the current status and terminology relating each VITALISE living lab (1) use cases and research users, (2) availability of technology assisted data collection approaches, (3) services and methods, (4) research process phases (5) innovation process phases and (6) living lab business model attributes. As a result, the following research questions were defined.

- RQ1: Who are the key research users and use cases in living lab research infrastructure?
- RQ2: What are the main data collection technologies in health and wellbeing living lab research?
- RQ3: What the main methods and tools utilized in in health and wellbeing living lab research?
- RQ4: What are the key research process phases in living lab research?
- RQ5: What are the key innovation process phases in living lab research?
- RQ6: What the main living lab business model attributes?

SAMPLE GROUP: The key experts and advisors from VITALISE consortium living labs

INPUTS: In practice, each living lab filled a six different excel files each file having the following clarifying questions as key measures:

RQ1: Key research users and user cases: (1) Researcher profile name (a single researcher or a group of researchers), (2) Researcher expertise / discipline (a single researcher or a group of researchers), (3) Brief use case description describing what kind of study this particular researcher(s) would in your opinion conduct, (4) Source of typical funding for the suggested study (e.g. fixed funding, H2020, national funding), (5) Whether a decision by an ethics committee is needed for that kind of study, if YES which committee.

RQ2: Main data collection technologies: (1) Data collection technology name, (2) Short description of the technology solution, (3) Object of data collection (keyword), (4) Equipment models

used by LL (if available), (5) Link to detailed specifications of the equipment (if available), (6) Output data format, (7) Discuss the possibilities and restrictions relating collecting open data with the technology and indicate if you have open data sets available collected by this technology

RQ3: Main methods, tools and services: Excel file's first two columns were prefilled and included a total of 33 different "Service title", and "Service description" items derived from Validation in Health project's (ProVaHealth) final report (Santonen, 2020). For each title and description, the following inputs were requested: (1) Suggested a new or modified title (leave blank if OK for your LL), (2) Mark as 1 if your LL is offering the service, (3) Give your LL additions, comments and improvement suggestions for service descriptions. By using similar data structure, living labs were also asked to add new living lab methods, tools and services not yet presented in the list. If the prefilled were considered okay, living labs were asked to leave a cell blank.

RQ4: The key research process phases: Excel file's first three columns (phase title, description, outcome) were prefilled by six research process items derived from VITALISE funding application. For each process phase the following inputs were requested: (1) Comments on phase title, (2) Comments on phase description, (3) Comments on phase outcomes. By using similar data structure, living labs were also asked to add new research process phases not yet presented in the list. If the prefilled were considered okay, living labs were asked to leave a cell blank

RQ5: The key innovation process phases: Excel file's first four columns (phase title, key activities, aim, outcome) were prefilled by six main research process items derived from VITALISE funding application. For each process phase the following inputs were requested: (1) Comments on process phase titles, (2) Comments on activities during the phase description, (3) Comments on the aim of the phase description and (4) Comments on the outcome of the phase description. By using similar data structure, living labs were also asked to add new innovation process phases not yet presented in the list. If the prefilled were considered okay, living labs were asked to leave a cell blank

RQ6: Main business model attributes: Living lab business model attributes grounded on business model canvas model (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010) and derived from Validation in Health project's (ProVaHealth) final report (Santonen, 2020) were prefilled into excel For each business model attribute the following inputs were requested: (1) title suggestion and (2) Additions and comments for existing attributes and descriptions including modification of the terms of phrasing. If the prefilled were considered okay, living labs were asked to leave a cell blank

BACKGROUND AND STIMULATION MATERIALS: Besides the descriptions derived from product Validation in Health project's (ProVaHealth) final report (Santonen, 2020) and VITALISE funding application, a conceptual matrix user-interface illustrated in Figure 1 was also included to background materials. The "matrix" defines a list of questions, which VITALISE project should be able to answers once the harmonization process at the end of project has been completed. Living labs were suggested imagining themselves clicking one of the questions and thinking about what they would personally like to see as an answer.

	LL 1 ----- LL n	S1 ----- Sn	T1 ----- Tn	UG1 ----- UGn	BM1 ----- BMn	IP1 ----- IPn	RP1 ----- RPn
Uniquely named LIVING LABS / infra structures their description Living lab / infra name 1 ⋮ Living lab n		What services and methods LL/infra is offering?	What data collection Technologies LL/infra is offering?	What kind of end-user groups LL/infra is able to reach?	What is LL / infra business model?	What innovation process phases LL can cover?	What services LL is offering in given research process phase?
Uniquely named SERVICES / METHODS and their description Service/ method 1 ⋮ Service n		What services and methods LL/infra is offering?	What data collection technologies service is utilizing ?	What kind of end-user groups can be engaged in the service?	How services and business models are linked?	What services LL is offering in given innovation process phase?	What services LL is offering in given research process phase?
Uniquely named DATA COLLECTION TECHNOLOGIES description Data collection technology 1 ⋮ Technology n		What data collection technologies LL/infra is offering?	What data collection technologies given service is utilizing ?	What kind of data collection technologies can be used with the end-user group?	How data collection technologies and business models are linked?	What data collection technologies can be utilized in given innovation process phase?	What data collection technologies can be utilized in given research process phase
Uniquely named END-USER GROUPS and their descriptions (i.e. testees) End-user group 1 ⋮ User group n		What kind of end-user groups LL / infra is able to reach?	What kind of end-user groups can be engaged in the given service?	What kind of data collection technologies can be used with the end-user group?	How end-user groups and business models are linked?	What kind of user-groups are available for given innovation process phase?	What kind of user-groups are available for given research process phase?
Uniquely named BUSINESS MODEL ATTRIBUTES and their descriptions Business model attribute 1 ⋮ BM attributen		What is LL / infra business model?	How services and business models are linked?	How data collection technologies and business models are linked?	How end-user groups and business models are linked?	How business model is linked with innovation process phases?	How business model is linked with research process phases?
Uniquely named INNOVATION PROCESS PHASES and their descriptions Innovation process phase 1 ⋮ Process phase n		What innovation process phases LL can cover?	What services LL is offering in given innovation process phase?	What data collection technologies can be utilized in given innovation process phase?	What kind of user-groups are available for given innovation process phase?	How business model is linked with innovation process phases?	How innovation and research process phases are linked?
Uniquely named RESEARCH PROCESS PHASES and their descriptions Research process phase 1 ⋮ Process phase n		What research process phases LL can cover?	What services LL is offering in given research process phase?	What data collection technologies can be utilized in given research process phase	What kind of user-groups are available for given research process phase?	How business model is linked with research process phases?	How innovation and research process phases are linked?

Figure 2 Conceptual matrix by Santonen to illustrate the interlinkage between the key dimensions of living labs

PERFORMED ACTIVITIES: Before starting the data collection at the VITALISE consortium level, AUTH living lab pilot tested the data collection process. Based on the pilot test, the following data collection guidelines were provided for living labs:

1. If possible, ask your relevant living lab team members individually make additions to the provided excel files.
2. Afterwards arrange a workshop with your teammates and discuss the responses and refine your living lab contributions. Since there is a lot of content in excel files, it is assumed that workshop should last at least 3 hours. This, however, would require that individual team members have done the prefilling and get familiar with the responses before the workshop. If prefilling is not done, we expect that workshop will require clearly more than 3 hours.
3. Start filling the excel files by defining the use-cases in order to understand what kind need your research customers could have. Later, the harmonization process, we will verify if your assumptions are correct. When thinking about users in the use cases think about individual researchers, but also multidisciplinary research teams.
4. Evaluate the existing services descriptions and add your services or modify the existing ones. Check the services against the use case examples. Also, if you notice a service which is required to fulfil the use case needs, please add the service even if you are not providing it. Indicate this in the service description (e.g., not yet provided service or planning to provide).
5. List all your data collection technologies including those which you are not going to use in the Joint Research Activities (JRAs).
6. Fill the research process phase excel. Use your prior research project experiences as an evaluation framework for the phases. Also think about the forthcoming JRA studies in context of research process. Then double check the service list and verify that all services required by the different research process phases are listed.
7. Fill the innovation process phase excel based on same principles as in the case of research process.
8. Finally, make your modifications and additions to business model excel. We especially looking for value proposition contributions since that is currently the weakest part in the BM

instrument. Please notify that BM attributes are defined based on living lab providing R&D services for SMEs. Therefore, evaluate the attribute list from the following two viewpoints: (1) living lab providing services for scientific research community to do research and (2) living lab providing services for non-scientific communities (e.g., for companies, public authorities) to develop products, services and processes.

2.2.2 Workshop for evaluation process

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS: Define the evaluation process and tools that will be used for assessing the status of each Living Lab, and how this will be applied. This workshop was aiming to do the first steps towards understanding of the categories and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for creating a Harmonized way of assessing the Living Labs maturity.

SAMPLE GROUP: Living Lab researchers and practitioners beyond the VITALISE consortium partners.

INPUTS: The inputs used for this session was derived from the ongoing work of ENoLL and FLLSA towards the creation of an evaluation framework. A presentation and a Miro board were created in order to guide the workshop participants.

BACKGROUND AND STIMULATION MATERIALS: The tool for Living Labs self-evaluation designed by FLLSA and the living lab network members (Annex 1) was used as a starting point for ideation among the workshop organizers. ENoLL is also designing a tool to evaluate its network that was also used as stimulation of the general workshop approach.

PERFORMED ACTIVITIES: The workshop was divided into two thematic areas based on the objectives. As a first step the participants were asked to identify the domains in which a living lab will be evaluated. A list of already identified domains was given and participants were asked to add new domains that they thought were missing. The proposed domains were 1) multidisciplinary approach, 2) Harmonization/standardization of procedures & policies, 3) Direct engagement of people, 4) Access to RI's, 5) harmonization of tools and technologies, 6) transnational collaboration, 7) knowledge sharing and capacity building, 8) common understanding, 9) societal impact, 10) economic impact. After that the participants were asked to vote for their preferred domains. Then participants were divided into small groups and were asked to work on a specific domain and try to identify KPIs that can help to follow the progress of a Living Lab.

2.2.3 Harmonization Workshop

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS: The aim of the workshop was to develop an initial version and understanding of how the analysis is being done and discuss more specifically on the services for which the living labs did not reach a consensus.

SAMPLE GROUP: Living Lab researchers and practitioners beyond the VITALISE consortium partners.

INPUTS: The preliminary results that came out of the Living Lab responses to the Excel files regarding the researchers use cases, the data collection classification, the services, and procedures offered by Living Labs, as well as the research and innovation process phases and the LL's business model

BACKGROUND AND STIMULATION MATERIALS: The background materials used were the analysed and concatenated results of the written comments in excels collected by the VITALISE consortium partners.

PERFORMED ACTIVITIES: During the first Harmonization Workshop that was carried out on July 1st, 2021, activities performed in Task 2.1 were initially discussed and, specifically, the use case examples provided by the Living Labs involved. In first place, the preliminary categories that occurred after the quantitative analysis were presented, based on the answers given from the Living Labs and then, followed a constructive discussion in order to come to a consensus regarding this categorization. At the second phase, the consensus rules were presented and discussed with the

consortium. Finally, an open discussion was held about the services' names that did not reach the consensus threshold in the first written comments round.

2.2.4 VITALISE Living Lab Interviews

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS: The objective of this step was to gain a deeper understanding of which services each living lab is providing and in what way. As sometimes the description of a service might not be that representative, when discussing specific examples, it is more effective to reach a deeper understanding of what each living lab is doing in their everyday work.

SAMPLE GROUP: Living Labs of the VITALISE consortium

INPUTS: The initial excel file with the written information provided by each living lab.

PERFORMED ACTIVITIES: During the period of summer but also during September, some interviews were conducted with all the living labs in the VITALISE consortium. Some representatives attended from each Living Lab (1-4 people) that know the operations of the Living Lab well and know what it can provide to external users. In the beginning of this process, the first thing was to briefly present the use cases categories that occurred after the quantitative analysis of the responses given from the Living Labs and the Harmonization workshop, in order to come to a consensus upon them. The aim was to understand whether it was okay for the interviewed Living Lab to keep the existing categories as such, or if they had something else to add or to propose. The next step was to discuss and clarify some points about the services, one by one, to see each Living Lab's point of view, by asking to elaborate and give some examples from their experience.

2.2.5 Online Engagement of the Living Lab Community Workshop

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS: The aim of this session during the Digital Living Lab Days was to share and exchange ideas, knowledge and information about different tools, methods templates, canvases, approaches and scientific instruments used in several services by the Living Labs.

SAMPLE GROUP: The entire consortium, but also the external Living Labs, as well as everyone interested in the LL's harmonization methodology attended the Digital Living Lab Days.

INPUTS: The results collected during the first period in the VITALISE project, regarding the several services, tools, methods and terms used by the Living Labs involved in the project.

PERFORMED ACTIVITIES: The session was conducted during the annual gathering of the global Living Lab community, Digital Living Lab Days (DLLD 2021), inspired by the initial results of the VITALISE project regarding the process of Harmonizing Living Labs. In this context, the methodology of the VITALISE Harmonization process and the several steps that will be followed during this dynamic and iterative procedure, including its schematic depiction was presented, and the participants shared their views on the methodology. The next part at this session, was an interactive discussion and a workshop that took place, aiming to create a common understanding about the services and tools each Living Lab is using. For this purpose, the participants were asked to join a mentimeter presentation, in order to share their opinions and ideas about some tools, methods, templates, canvases, approaches and/or scientific instruments that they are aware of, regarding some particular services (co-creation workshops, idea testing, presentation and description of the concepts & prototypes for the target group, qualitative and/or quantitative feedback collection, qualitative and/or quantitative feedback collection directly from end-users or other stakeholders, large-scale real-life testing, piloting & demonstrations).

3 Results from state of the art analysis

All the steps presented in Section 2.2 were performed in a linear way and the outputs of a step were considered as inputs for the next step. This Section summarizes the results for the different categories of data that were measured in order to result to the first Standard Version.

3.1 Overview of initial results

The initial idea was to collect and structure the data in the Standard in 6 general categories: 1) key research users and user cases of living lab research infrastructures, 2) main data collection technologies and data categories used in health and wellbeing living lab research, 3) main services, methods, tools and scientific instrument utilized in living lab research, 4) key research process phases in living lab research 5) key innovation process phases in living lab research, 6) main living lab business model attributes. However, the first round of collected feedback (Gathering comments on definitions) showed that the participants were not very familiar with research and innovation phases and business model attributes. Also, the comments gathered from the 1st workshop focused on the importance of the definition of services, methods and tools and considered the phases as a second step of analysis for the categorization of the services, methods and tools. Based on those comments and the restricted time, the analysis following the Harmonization workshop was focused on the three first domains.

Some very interesting insights came from the one-to-one interviews with Living Labs about the services and tools used. Some common aspects that were discussed are summarized below:

- Confusion between services, methods and tools:

A first point worth mentioning is that with almost all Living Labs a constructive conversation was made regarding whether the current services are actually services or tools/methodologies. So, on the one hand, there was the idea that interviews, focus groups etc. might be more a kind of tool, used to achieve a specific purpose and, on the other hand, that they could possibly be considered as separate services provided by the Living Labs. In general, the ones considered as tools (namely: interviews and focus groups, surveys, Observations, shadowing and ethnography studies, Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards), Hackathon and design sprints) are used for a purpose described in the other services (e.g. impact assessment) and are not standalone. However, if we create a list of services that a Living Lab can provide, all agreed that it would be nice to have the tools as well, but maybe distinguish. A general assumption was that these two (services and methods) are closely related and linked, and that, most of the times, they are not provided separately. Moreover, for some services there was also the idea of splitting them up into more different services and for some others it was proposed to rename or reframe them.

- Provided services and tools should be organized into phases (in each phase of the research process and/or innovation process what services are used). There is also some confusion related to phase names.

An example can be the service of briefing that was later renamed to Intake and matching. In the beginning of this service there is a first meet with the “customer” which results to an offer/plan, then a service exploration is conducted, as well as co-creations among several experts. After approval by the “customer”, a document/contract is signed and in the end some follow up meetings are conducted. So, this is a broader service that can depict a whole category.

Another relevant example had to do with the co-creation workshop service, mentioning that it is like a whole separate phase (a very broad category) which is usually at the beginning of the innovation process and can include various methodologies.

- The several services and processes highlighted the fact that they are personalized to each stakeholder

In other words, emphasis was given on the fact that the services and the methodologies provided refer to a very personalized process, adjusted every time on the specific “stakeholder” (can also be referred as “customer”) and his needs/preferences and that’s why it might be better to be described in a way that gives the basic idea/guidelines, but also leaves space to each Living Lab to make the appropriate adjustments (based on each “customer”).

During the activities performed of the first state of the art analysis of Living Labs, the need for new additions in the conceptual framework of Living Labs has arisen. All the input from the various activities performed was collected and taken into consideration in order to define the first version of the Living Lab Standard concept overview (Figure 3 –Section 4) for Living Labs management. However, not all categories were analysed in the first state of the art analysis phase. All the key elements will be prepared in an iterative way aiming to provide a stable version at the end of the VITALISE project that will continue improving.

The sections below summarize the results of all the analysis that was performed for the three first domains (1) research users and user cases, 2) data collection technologies and data categories, 3) main services, methods, tools and scientific instruments).

3.2 Use cases and potential end-users

A quantitative content analysis was conducted based on the responses given by the Living Labs. For that purpose, all the information from the responses about the researchers’ expertise was gathered, examined one by one and compared to each other in order to create some preliminary categories. A table was created, with the categories found (names of the researcher’ expertise), how many times they were mentioned by different Living Labs and the exact descriptions/terms used by the Living Labs for each of these categories. This categorization was, then, discussed during the first Harmonization Workshop in order to come to a consensus among the Living Labs and, it was, also, discussed during the interviews conducted with each one of them, aiming to clarify some points by asking more specific information and examples about some of the use cases mentioned from their side. So, after the implementation/conduction of the interviews so far, we renamed two of the existing categories and we also added a new one. In particular, the category “Experts in recreational interventions” was renamed “Experts in performing arts”, the category “Business oriented researchers” was renamed “Business developers”, and the new category added was the one named “Data scientists”. The result of this process was to come up with 21 final categories of researchers’ expertise that all Living Labs agreed on. The user types and use cases are described in Living lab standard version 0.1 PART2: Customer segments. In the following rounds, more in-depth use case definitions must be made.

3.3 Data collection devices, technologies and data types

The VITALISE Living Labs provided information about the data collection equipment available in their entity and a description of the type of data they gather in the different experiments. The requested and collected information included: Data collection technology name, short description, Object of data collection (keyword), equipment models used by LL (if available), link to detailed specifications of the equipment (if available), output data format and to indicate if there were Open data sets available. 7 out of 10 Living Labs provided the information.

AUTH and ENOLL analysed it separately. The data analysis took place in 3 steps, depicted in the following diagram:

The data analysis consisted of extracting the data collection equipment names and types of uses from the provided descriptions. AUTH and ENOLL made a matrix with categories and subcategories to classify all the technologies and their use. To classify the technologies in categories, both teams had the following approach:

To classify the technologies in categories, both teams had the following approach:

After this exercise, both entities reviewed the results and integrated a final version including:

- Subcategories can be allocated in multiple categories
- Subcategories present in other categories are marked differently
- Deletion of unnecessary categories
- Modification of the category names

The analysis concluded with 8 categories and 63 subcategories of data that are gathered from living labs using various technologies.

Categories:

1. Activity tracking/monitoring
2. Assisting technology
3. Biometrics
4. Biosignals
5. Cognitive function
6. Environment/context
7. Physiological monitoring
8. Virtual reality/interactive technology

Subcategories:**Table 4 Data collection subcategories**

1	Activities of Daily Living	33	Lifestyle recommendations
2	Activity Level	34	Luminosity
3	Adjust treatments and therapy	35	Metabolic testing
4	Air quality sensor	36	Movement measurement
5	Alarm system	37	Natural Language Understanding
6	Alternative and augmentative Interaction	38	Nutritional recommendations
7	Basic biometrics	39	Orientation
8	Big data collection	40	Oxygen saturation
9	Blind operation	41	Patient history & demographics
10	Blood oxygen	42	Physical activity
11	Blood sugar level	43	Physical performance
12	Body Battery	44	Physiological and behavioural biomarkers
13	Body Position	45	Planes of pelvic movement
14	Calories burned	46	Posture Movement
15	Capture Cognitive activities performance	47	Robotic hand control
16	Cognitive training	48	Safe bathroom usage
17	Concentration levels PM1	49	Safe walk assistance
18	Concentration levels PM10	50	Sleep Quality
19	Concentration levels PM2.5	51	Speech analysis and intuitive user interface
20	Door operation	52	Speech recognition
21	EEG	53	Steps
22	Electrophysiological timeseries	54	Stress Level
23	Energy expenditure	55	Technical alerts (Flood)
24	Gait	56	Technical alerts (Smoke)
25	Getting into and out of bed	57	Technical alerts (Temperature)
26	Heart disease	58	Temperature monitoring
27	Heart failure	59	Usage habits
28	Home sensor monitoring	60	Virtual reality
29	Human balance	61	Web Interaction
30	Indoor movements	62	Weight BMI
31	Inverse kinematics data	63	Well-being of elder people
32	Ischemic episode data		
33	Lifestyle recommendations		
34	Luminosity		

Example visualization cross- checked categories

Several subcategories are related to a general category as presented in the example visualization below. A database of technologies for the specific subcategories was also created. This database will be further improved throughout the Harmonization process.

color code	category	includes	includes2	includes22	includes3	includes4	includes5	includes6	includes7	includes8
	Activity tracking/monitoring	Body Battery	Body Posisiton	Body posture	calories burned	Gait	Energy expenditure	Human balance	Inverse kinematics data	Movement measurement
	Assisting technology	Alarm system	Distance with the user	Engaged users	Engaged users	Intent and entity identification	location	Natural Language Understanding	Safe bathroom usage	Safe walk assistance
	Biometrics	Basic biometrics	Heart rate							
	Biosignals	Electrophysiologic al timeseries	EEG	ECG	VO2 max					
	Cognitive fuction	Cognitive training								
	Environment/context	Concentration levels PM1	Concentration levels PM2.5		Concentration levels PM10	Blind operation	Alarm system	Door operation	Technical alerts (Flood)	Technical alerts (Smoke)
	Physiological monitoring	Energy expenditure	Patient history & demographics		Weight BMI	Blood oxygen	Blood sugar level			
	Virtual reality/interactive technology	Virtual reality	Web interaction	Gesture detection (smile)	Alternative and augmentative interaction	Speech analysis and intuitive user interface	Patient history & demographics			

A researcher using the specific database can search for the general category, then the subcategory he is interested on and the available technologies in the living labs that can gather this input. The identified devices and technologies are described in Living lab standard version 0.1 PART 7B: Devices and technologies.

3.4 Methods, Tools and Services

During the first data collection phase, VITALISE living labs were asked to provide comments on methods, tools and services derived from Product Validation in Health project’s (ProVaHealth) final report as described by Santonen (2020). The initial list consisted of a total of 33 different items. The consensus about each item title and description was evaluated by calculating how many living labs were provided title or description comments (NOTE: this evaluation should be considered as an indicative result, since living labs were not notified beforehand about the agreement procedure). During this stage, nine out of eleven living labs filled the excel files. In Table 5, the consensus levels for each item’s title and description are presented.

Table 5 Consensus levels among VITALISE living labs (N=9)

METHODS/TOOLS/SERVICES NAME	TITLE COMMENTS COUNT	DESCRIPTION COMMENTS COUNT	COMMENTS COUNT SUMMARY	LEVEL OF AGREEMENT TITLE	LEVEL OF AGREEMENT DESCRIPTION
1. Access to data	0	4	4	100 %	56 %
2. Briefing	3	4	7	67 %	56 %
3. Capacity building	1	4	5	89 %	56 %
4. Clinical trials and regulatory approval tests	1	4	5	89 %	56 %
5. Co-creation workshop	0	3	3	100 %	67 %
6. Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	1	4	5	89 %	56 %
7. Concept and proof-of-concept tests – feasibility study	1	3	4	89 %	67 %
8. Customer journey	1	3	4	89 %	67 %
9. Equipment and facility rental service	0	4	4	100 %	56 %
10. Expert opinion, sparring and advisory services	1	3	4	89 %	67 %
11. Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	0	4	4	100 %	56 %
12. Funding	2	4	6	78 %	56 %
13. Grant writing and funding application support service	0	3	3	100 %	67 %
14. Hackathon and design sprints	0	2	2	100 %	78 %
15. Idea selection and testing	1	3	4	89 %	67 %
16. Impact assessment and validation test	0	3	3	100 %	67 %
17. Innovation network orchestration	0	3	3	100 %	67 %
18. Interviews and focus groups	0	2	2	100 %	78 %
19. Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	0	1	1	100 %	89 %
20. Legal, regulation and safety standard support	1	4	5	89 %	56 %
21. Living lab project planning and management	0	3	3	100 %	67 %
22. Marketing and sales support	0	3	3	100 %	67 %
23. Observations, shadowing and ethnography studies	2	3	5	78 %	67 %
24. Panel research	3	3	6	67 %	67 %
25. Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	0	4	4	100 %	56 %
26. Prototyping test	0	0	0	100 %	100 %
27. Public procurement support services	0	2	2	100 %	78 %
28. Simulation test	1	2	3	89 %	78 %
29. Small-scale real life testing and experimentation	0	0	0	100 %	100 %
30. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	1	2	3	89 %	78 %
31. Surveys	0	3	3	100 %	67 %
32. Usability testing	1	3	4	89 %	67 %
33. User personas	0	2	2	100 %	78 %

As result, all titles reached at least simple majority level, which can be considered a promising outcome. In all 93.8% of the title names (N=29) reached strong supermajority level and two items (6.1%) supermajority level. The remaining two items (6.1%) reached simple majority level. Also, in the case of descriptions, all items reached at least simple majority level. However, only 27.3% of descriptions reached supermajority level (i.e., 9.1% strong supermajority and 18.2% supermajority). Nearly three quarters (72.7%, N=24) of the descriptions reached simple majority level. The popularity of the above identified methods, tools and services among VITALISE living labs are presented in Table 6 (NOTE: Clinical trials and regulatory approval tests are separated in the table).

Table 6 Methods, tools and services popularity among VITALISE living labs (N=11)

Rank	Method/Service name (and alphabetical ID number)	LLs N	LLs %	AIT	AUTH	CERTH	GAIA- Ozeanlab	GAIA- SilverLab	INTRAS	LAUREA	LICALAB	MCGILL	TREBAG	UPM
	<i>N Total</i>			27	24	17	32	32	30	30	19	20	16	25
	<i>% Total</i>			79 %	71 %	50 %	94 %	94 %	87 %	88 %	56 %	59 %	47 %	74 %
1	19. Interviews and focus groups	11	100 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	22. Living lab project planning and management	11	100 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	30. Small-scale real life testing and experimentation	11	100 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	31. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	11	100 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	32. Surveys	11	100 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	2. Briefing	10	91 %	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6	11. Expert opinion, sparring and advisory services	10	91 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1
6	18. Innovation network orchestration	10	91 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1
6	20. Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	10	91 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1
10	6. Co-creation workshop	9	82 %	1	1		1	1		1	1	1	1	1
10	9. Customer journey	9	82 %	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1		1
10	16. Idea selection and testing	9	82 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1
10	17. Impact assessment and validation test	9	82 %	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1		1
10	25. Panel research	9	82 %	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1		1
10	27. Prototyping test	9	82 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1
10	29. Simulation test	9	82 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1		1
10	33. Usability testing	9	82 %	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1
10	34. User personas	9	82 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1
19	8. Concept and proof-of-concept tests – feasibility study	8	73 %	1	1		1	1	1	1	1			1
19	14. Grant writing and funding application support service	8	73 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1	
19	15. Hackathon and design sprints	8	73 %	1	1	1	1	1	1	1				1
19	24. Observations, shadowing and ethnography studies	8	73 %	1			1	1	1	1	1	1		1
23	1. Access to data	7	64 %		1		1	1	1		1		1	1
23	3. Capacity building	7	64 %		1				1	1	1	1	1	1
23	4. Clinical trials	7	64 %	1	1	1	1	1	1			1		1
23	7. Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	7	64 %	1			1	1		1	1		1	1
27	5. regulatory approval tests	6	55 %	1		1	1	1	1			1		
27	10. Equipment and facility rental service	6	55 %		1		1	1		1			1	1
29	21. Legal, regulation and safety standard support	5	45 %				1	1	1	1			1	
30	12. Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	4,5	41 %	1			1	1	0,5	1				
31	23. Marketing and sales support	4	36 %				1	1	1	1				
31	26. Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	4	36 %				1	1	1	1				
31	28. Public procurement support services	4	36 %	1		1			1	1				
34	13. Funding	2	18 %				1	1						

Furthermore, 10 new items presented in Table 7 were also suggested, but consensus among them was not evaluated during this process. The additional suggestions are not included in Standard on that phase but will be considered in the Co-creation phase of the first harmonization cycle.

Table 7 New living lab method, tool and service suggestion

Method/Tool/Service title	Description
Measurement of social, environmental and socioeconomic impact	Measurement of social, environmental and socioeconomic impact through SROI methodology - Support to measure the impact of applied methodologies and technologies including outcomes that do not have a market value. SROI is conducted in four steps: 1) development of an impact map, identifying inputs, valuing inputs, clarifying outputs and describing outcomes; 2) Evidence outcomes and giving them a value; 3) Establishing impact; 4) Calculating SROI and reporting

Longitudinal data collection	A longitudinal study is a research design involving repeated observations of the same variables (e.g., people) over short or long periods of time. In here long period (i.e. multiple years is referred).
Ethical approval support	Ethical review and approval application consulting and/or writing it as a service
Research design/protocol definition	Includes research design and protocol definition and/or innovation process definition for research and development project
"Technology" and scientific research results transfer/consulting services	Helping to commercialize scientific results including e.g. patent and trademark processes, finding partners and clients.
Cross-border collaboration facilitation	Facilitating cross-border living lab research activities among multiple living labs (e.g. project coordinator or named entity responsible for this kind of collaboration).
Procurement up-scaling	Procurement scaling after accepted by one public authority. Includes also cross-border support and best practice transfers.
Innovation transfer	Planning and executing scalability and transferability after the originating living lab process has finished.
Data management planning	Support and consulting the data management planning process.

Some additional comments that were gathered from living lab interviews are listed below:

- Capacity building

A suggestion that has been made is that maybe this service would be better to be divided into different services. For example, 1) Site visits (maybe it is also a sub-category of marketing/dissemination), 2) Capacity building (training/knowledge transfer), 3) Publication service guidance/preparation (consulting about the whole process). Another suggestion made was to rename the service "capacity building programs" (because programs are usually longer in time and consist of several workshops, events, seminars) and the rest ("events/seminars", "site visits", "publishing") could be the methodologies for this service.

- Co-creation workshop

Living labs referred to the fact that "co-creation workshop" is a very broad category, like a whole separate phase -usually at the beginning of the innovation process-, and that it can include many methodologies (so maybe the name should be changed). A distinction was also made between co-creation session and focus group (or demo session, as they call it), highlighting that a session is something limited in time, also offered as service, and a focus group is more of an evaluation, mostly at the end of the innovation process or previously for need finding sessions.

- Concept and proof-of-concept tests – feasibility study

The term "assessment" instead of "test" was proposed, considering that testing is something more "practical" whereas assessment is a broader term. This service refers to a personalized process, scheduled with the specific "customer" and it is based on his needs/preferences. There are various methodologies that can be used for this purpose (e.g., interviews, questionnaires, wizard of oz etc.).

- Customer journey

This service was mentioned to be possibly interlinked with "Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking", as it is not usually offered individually but along with other innovation, ideation and business services (it is not often that a client request a customer journey map). Similarly, it was mentioned that customer journey is often included in co-creation sessions and not as a separate service, so maybe it should be considered as part of methodology. This service is mostly offered as a technique to the companies/researchers (rather than a service) once they understand what they want.

- Impact assessment and validation test

Concerning this service, it was expressed the opinion that it is not clearly defined (it is not clear what exactly the word "impact" means, or if it is referred to long-term or short-term effects). It was proposed that maybe it would be better to split into two different services (1. "assessment" and 2. "validation test").

- Innovation network orchestration

One LL commented that they work as referral to the network, but it is not a service provided.

- Interviews and focus groups

Most of the interviewees indicated that interviews and focus groups might be better considered as a tool, as a methodology that is used in various services and not as a standalone service. A suggestion made was that in that case, "workshops" could be the service and "interviews and focus groups" the methodology.

- Large-scale real-life testing and piloting & Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation

Maybe there is no reason to make a quantitative discrimination between large-scale and small-scale testing, as the number of test participants is not the most crucial factor and it's something that is also quite subjective (where do we put the limit between small/large scale). For instance, apart from the number of participants, it also has to do with the effort so it was suggested that the service could be renamed "Real life testing and piloting" and then, in a next stage, it could be defined for each case if it would be large-scale or small-scale.

- Living lab project planning and management

An opinion expressed about "Living lab project planning and management" is that it might have the same outcome with the debriefing, and that, maybe, only "management" should be considered as a separate service. Moreover, they suggested that this service probably needs to be rephrased for referring to externals (because normally we work for our Living Labs, not for externals). Similarly, they mentioned that this is only being done internally for projects, and externally it is offered as a service only to local authorities and hospitals (strategic partners).

- Observations, shadowing and ethnography studies

Observational studies are something completely different from ethnography studies and suggested that they could be spited up (maybe ethnography is used more as a technique). This can be considered more of a technique/methodology and is maybe the same (or similar) with focus groups.

- Usability testing

One point, highlighted by LICALAB was that the description of this service seems to fit more on a test-bed. In that context, it was proposed that human factor study could be a separate service.

- Surveys

Surveys can be considered as a different tool, used for different purposes, for assessing something (while the previous tools are for discussion), and it was proposed that maybe it should be joined with questionnaires in a new category: “surveys and questionnaires”.

- User personas

User personas can be considered a methodology instead of a service.

- Access to data

Generally, it was highlighted that in most, cases data is collected from the LL, sometimes in an occasional, ad-hoc basis, usually without public access (need to be an agreement about the data, if the can/cannot be shared or reused for other means, if it is needed a consent or registration etc.) but in some cases the data can be also collected in a public, accessible database, depending each time from the specific case.

- Briefing

It was mentioned as an important and methodic process in order to get to know with the client/customer and create an individualized plan, based on his/her needs. It can take the form of either an open discussion or a more targeted interview and can last one or more days (first meet, offer/plan, services exploration, co-creation of several expertise, document/contract, follow up meetings and activities).

- Equipment and facility rental service

In general, some Living Labs reported that they often rent spaces for lectures etc. in a win-to-win agreement. Furthermore, most LLs referred to human resources rent.

- Expert opinion, sparring and advisory services

Regarding this service, it was generally mentioned that each Living Lab has a wide network and multidisciplinary collaborations. For example, collaborations with universities/academic experts, pharmacy, doctors, healthcare professionals, policy makers, highlighting that the experts are mainly requested by the client, but some consultation is offered from the LL as well. It is quite rare for Living Labs to pay external people for restricted period of time, only if it is very time-consuming/ long procedure/specific expertise, explaining that the professional work is paid, but, in general, consultation is for free.

4 Standard Version 0.1

This Section will be the first public version of Living Labs Standard. This Standard is considered Version 0.1 as the information included in this standard have not yet undergone a full cycle of Harmonization. This Standard depicts the expertise and the feedback gathered only from VITALISE consortium Living Labs. This Section is structured in such a way so that it can be separated from the rest of the deliverable and published in the VITALISE website.

4.1 Introduction

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) – an international non-profit association promoting and enhancing user-driven innovation ecosystem defines living lab is “a user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings” (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>).

The aim of this Living Lab standard is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices. Establishing Living Lab management system, they will

1. promote the expansion and growth of Living Lab movement beyond current actors and customers,
2. stimulate cross-organization and transnational research collaboration,
3. enable data sharing and comparison of the research results,
4. increase research quality, and
5. define a common terminology and language among researchers and practitioners.

The Figure 3 defines the conceptual overview of the living lab management system presented in this standard document.

Figure 3 The key elements and conceptual overview of the living lab management system

The following key elements will concern the Living Lab community and will be further assessed in the next Standard Version.

1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) – terms and definitions: LLL introduces, lists and shortly defines a comprehensive catalogue of terms associated and included in different parts of the living lab

standard (i.e. 2 to 9). The LLL is grounded on Wikipedia type of user interface, where definitions including overlapping terminology, will enable quick jumping between different descriptions and to in-depth descriptions in other standard sections. LLL will help to discuss living lab related issues among the different stakeholder, who currently are using varying terminology.

2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM): “A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The purpose of the LLBM part is to identify different attributes associated with each nine BMC element. Having a unified way to describe LLBM, enables quantitative business model comparison between different living labs as well as open ups possibilities to track changes in business model strategies.

3. Research process: Living lab research process part focuses on defining the key steps to execute and define a living lab research methodology. The part is comprised of (1) a common template to define research protocol, (2) ethical and data management plans, (3) participant recruitment procedures, (4) infrastructure selection procedure, (5) data collection procedures, (6) data analysis and comparison practices and (7) fair data practices for opening data. Each phase consists of aim, outcome and maturity level description. Furthermore, research process phases are interlinked other living lab standard parts in order to identify which other items are relevant for each research process phase. Having a standard way to describe living lab research design, helps developing a unified research methodology, which enables a robust results comparison a cross the different studies and increases the research quality.

4. Innovation process: Living lab innovation process part focuses on defining in an unambiguous way, the different innovation management process phases which are or can be covered during the living lab data collection phase. This part defines an iterative and agile user-centered innovation and design process and align the phases with Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept. TRL is widely adopted concept to describe developed solution maturity level. Respectively to research process, different innovation process phases are interlinked other living lab standard parts in order to identify which of the other items are relevant for each process phase. Each phase key activities, aim, methods, outcome and TRL maturity level description.

5. R&D services: R&D services part defines a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its’ customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities or parts of the Living Lab standard, needed to accomplish living lab R&D project as whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. In longer run, the aim is to define the Minimum Acceptable Service Level for each service type in order ensure service quality across the different living labs.

6. Living lab Research Infrastructure (RI): This part provides a classification schema and definitions for different types of living lab infrastructures. In regulation No 1291/2013, European Union Parliament and Council of the European Union (2013) defines RIs as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. The definitions and descriptions for (1) single-sited, (2) distributed, (3) virtual and (4) mobile living lab facilities are provided.

7. Data collection approaches. Data collection approaches consists of the following three sub-parts: (1) methods and tools, (2) devices and technologies and (3) validated questionnaires and instruments. This part provides a collection of practical data collection approaches, which can be combined in multiple variation when defining a living lab project research methodology. *7A Methods and tools* part identifies and describes the different types of specific research methods, tools, and practices, which can be used for data collection during a living lab project. Among these are e.g. interviews, workshops and surveys. In the future, the standard will used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular method in different living research contexts.

7B Devices and technologies defines a commonly used technological solutions to collect and analyse living lab research data. Correspondingly to 7A methods and devices, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular technology in a research setting. *7C. Validated questionnaires and instrument* consists of a bunch of scientifically validated surveys, scales, interventions or similar, which are known to reliably measure certain phenomenon. Standard will promote especially questionnaires and instrument which are multilingual and freely available. If multiple instruments are available to measure same phenomenon, standard will make recommendation to make selections.

The structure followed in this deliverable includes information about the proposed title and description of the work along with Key characteristics, Pre-tasks: Participants' role, Objectives, Methods and Tools/online tools: It is common that a set of information is not yet identified for each service that is why some categories are removed from specific services.

To conclude, it is important to notice that the above described conceptual overview and the included key elements of the living lab management system are preliminary concepts. Therefore, the names, details and concept itself can be changed in follow-up versions.

4.2 Scope of this document

This is the first draft version of the Health and Wellbeing Living Labs Standard (Version 0.1). The structure and content of this document will be continuously improving and a new version will be released every 6 months. The information presented are a result of an analysis performed in the VITALISE project and more details about the analysis can be found in the Deliverables of the project. The rest of the document presents:

- **PART 2. Living lab business model:** The identified end users that can use the R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs
- **PART 5. R&D Services:** A list of R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs
- **PART 7A. Methods and tools:** In this standard version identified methods and tools are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions
- **PART 7B. Devices and technologies:** In this standard version identified devices and technologies are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions

4.3 PART 2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM)

"A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value" (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The living lab standard defines common attributes associated with each nine BMC element.

This standard version focuses on defining customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.

4.3.1 Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs

Below you can find the identified target-users for the services, methods and tools that Health and Wellbeing Living Labs provide.

Table 8 Researchers expertise

Researcher expertise	Brief use case description
Policy Makers	Studying the impact of new service models or new collaboration models in healthcare, designing or improving policies, gathering requirements for improving health and wellbeing of citizens, co-creation of research methodologies for policy making

Experts in communication studies	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab)
Computer/Technology Scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity
(Clinical, social, developmental, neuro-) Psychologists	Studying the behaviour and the mental wellbeing of participants, conducting psychometrics evaluation and real-life setting experimentation/observation/real life testing
Social workers/researchers	Conducting an investigation in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society
Researchers with clinical expertise	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g; via real life testing
Experts in UX research and assessment	Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behavior through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user's experience in different situations and while using different tools
Experts in sport science	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features
Experts in rehabilitation (physical, cognitive)	Physiology, physiotherapy, occupational health research, rehabilitation and prevention. Cognitive diseases assistive technology, neuromuscular rehabilitation assistive technology
Experts in performing arts	Creative health improvement (e.g. for cognitive decline) through music and dance (example: redesigning public spaces into healthy spaces: test and validate Smart methodologies, products and services through folk dance)
Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market

Pedagogues/educators	Evaluating different pedagogical approaches and their impact learning performance (especially in Simulation lab)
Experts in applied economics	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health
Experts in ergonomics and safety	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards
Citizen Scientists / users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation
Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g. for cognitive state)
Experts in accessibility Design	Validating accessible Architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations
Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behaviour and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation)
Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization
Experts in organizational studies	Co-creation, experimentation, organizational research, experts by experience / pier support included. Evaluation how multistakeholder collaboration and co-creation is done and how effective it is. Evaluates experimentations and experimentation culture. How users are involved into these processes
Data Scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations)

4.4 PART 5. R&D Services

R&D services part defines a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its' customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities, or parts of the Living Lab standard needed to accomplish a living lab R&D project as a whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type

of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. Living lab R&D services are classified into the following categories:

1. Networking and capacity building
2. Project planning and management
3. Market and competitor intelligence services
4. Co-creation
5. Testing and validation
6. Advisory services
7. Marketing and sales support

It is noted that some of the services can be included in multiple categories

4.4.1 Access to data

Description: Referring to service, which enables customers to access or retrieve data from one or more databases consisting of relevant data, based on mutual agreements respecting ethics and GDPR, which can be used for development or testing purposes.

R&D service categories: Market and competitor intelligence services

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Usually 2 sources: already existing data, new data collected
- Data must be anonymized and encrypted
- Consent from participants may also be needed
- Type of data: demographics/personal data, health-clinical data (e.g., cognitive, treatment changes, physical performance, care to rehabilitation), measure data, sensors' data (brain activity)
- For open data, FAIR data principles should be followed
- Ethical approval and GDPR processes when needed

Pre-tasks:

- Create a data gathering database, specific parameters of improvement
- Define the accessibility of the database (public or limited access) and how it is collected (in an integrated way or occasional/ad hoc databases/infrastructures)
- It is, usually, needed a request that is passed to the responsible of databases

4.4.2 Intake and matching

Description: During this service, the customer's (e.g., a company, SME, a start-up, a researcher) development and testing needs are clarified for the project planning purposes. It also includes the process of mapping the customer's needs and co-designing of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project and living lab capabilities to offer the particular project.

R&D service categories: Project planning and management

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Can be both open discussion or more focused
- Usually at the beginning of the research process
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- Duration varies-30 minutes (very short from) to few hours or days. In most of the cases there are multiple meetings taking place/more than one contact
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: Researchers, clinicians, customers, students

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Pre-tasks:

- Discuss and understand who are the customers and what are their needs.
- Agree to a plan -usually it is made a document/contract- (set goals, explore the different services, engage the operational team
- Revise & follow-up activities with the customer

Objectives

- Make a project proposal/offer
- Make a project contract

Named methods:

Client's needs elicitation methodology, interview/focus group/questionnaires for defining the project and collecting the needs, co-design of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project

4.4.3 Capacity building

Description: Training, knowledge sharing and awareness raising, site visits and event arrangement. Offering training for end-users and/or practitioners to improve their skills and knowledge about living lab approach, co-creation, iterative development and healthcare and wellbeing market. Stimulating knowledge sharing and awareness raising by publishing professional and scientific publications and arranging events, site visits and seminars.

R&D service categories: Networking and capacity building

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- The way of knowledge sharing and transfer depends on the project and on the purpose
- Use of short-term or long-term methods and courses
- Material can be both created for a purpose but also some available online

Participants' role:

- Service beneficiaries become trainees
- Living Labs can offer support for the design and facilitation of capacity building programs

Methods: Co-creation methodology, focus groups, training sessions (tech & non-tech), ethical training & legal in large scale settings, seminars, presentations, workshops, webinars, forums, websites and web-engines, events, site visits, publications, summer schools, degree program, methodological training, how to use new product

4.4.4 Clinical trials

Description: Clinical trials are experiments or observations done to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of new solution by monitoring its effects on large groups of people. Subjects are typically divided into two or more groups, one having "real treatment" by using the developed solution and the other group(s) using tried-and-true solution or not using any solution. The results are compared between the groups to evaluate the impacts.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Clinical trials are similar to impact assessment and validation test activities but follow more strict validation and approval process.

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Objectives

- To find out if new solution is safe and effective
- Get official approval for new solution

Methods:

- Has multiple phases and classes which depend on the developed solution

4.4.5 Co-creation session

Description: Workshop is a facilitated a group activity to find solutions for a specific problem by gathering ideas, solutions and insights from workshop participants while using variety of methods. Depending on the workshop focus, it may comprise ideation, concept development and testing. Typical duration for short workshop is from 45 minutes to 90 minutes, medium-length workshop from 90 minutes to 3 hours, and long-workshop from 3 hours to 1 day. The number of participants may vary depending on how many facilitators are available, and what kind of working methods are utilized. Typically, workshop facilitated by a single facilitator consist of six to eight persons. Number of participants are often even numbered to enable them to work in pairs.

R&D service categories: Co-creation

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Fundamental features: Requires (1) facilitator(s), (2) interaction/is interactive, (3) iterative process
- Can be applied in almost all phases: e.g., ideation, concept creation/testing, prototyping, prototype testing
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- It is a service but also a generic method
- Duration varies, but usually 2-3 hours
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: Researchers, clinicians, students (e.g., paediatric project, project on language and communication). Depending on the concept all actors of the quadruple helix are contacted, number of users depends also to the stakeholders. Engagement of different stakeholders can also be achieved by running series of sessions

Participants' role:

- In the beginning of the innovation process, involve the users as the creators
- If there is a product with higher TRL, a ready MVP is more like a focus group,
- Need finding session, focus group is more of an evaluation,

Pre-tasks: prepare session upfront with the sketches, if focus group - open questions (sent beforehand), workshop preparation template

Objectives (varies depending on researchers interest):

- Co-creation session: Finding solutions for a specific problem with or without prototypes or mock-ups. Co-creating the actual design, sketch interfaces, make the solution tangible, Drafting (prototypes, drawing, soft(adobe)), mockups
- Demo-session: specifically, setup to explain about the use of a prototype or market ready product and gather (first) feedback. Often done before launching a test.
- Business model session (broader, a service?): developing and defining a business model (e.g. potential customers, sales channels, distributors, value chain, the Willingness to Pay, revenue streams etc.

Methods: brainstorming, use simulations, group discussion / focus groups, Semi-structured focus group, survey, questionnaire

Tools: Projection walls, visual mockups, use tangible tools for prototyping (e.g. wearables), team groups, polling (tech); questionnaires, focus groups, idea generation techniques, post-it notes, creative supplies, art supplies,

Online tools: Online system for (idea generation platform, open), Teams meeting, Zoom with breakout rooms, Google meet, Miro whiteboard, Mural.co

4.4.6 Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking

Description: Quantitative and qualitative methods are used to evaluate the size of the market both, in volume and in value (also known as market studies). Customer segments, buying patterns, competition, and the economic environment are defined to identify the regulations and the barriers to entry. Defining the market by listing and describing current, future, direct and indirect competitors and analysing their competitive offering (e.g., SWOT) and user experience. Comparing offerings by measuring the performance of the developed products, services, or processes against those, which are considered to be the best in the industry. Can consist also literature reviews to a search and evaluate of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area.

R&D service categories: Market and competitor intelligence services

Participants' role: Competitors or interested in collaborations, can be done by students or experts.

Limitations: The study is no longer than ca 10 pages and is limited in operational workload to max 3 days, could apply only if transposed to a clinical or community research context

Objectives:

- identify the “space” for innovation, not analysing only specific segments, but also looking for new opportunities
- analyse market acceptance, support scalability and transferability potential, focus can be domestic/international/global market,
- identify direct and/or indirect competitors, qualitative or quantitative description of the market, focus can also be in research context or innovation management practices

Methods: Desk research, acquiring the information from the experts in the field, following the market as a job profile/duty, the people working know specific segments/areas, bibliometric studies, literature reviews to a search and evaluate of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area, technology exploitation, market analysis, benchmarking, other methods combined with interview(s) with a leading reference organisation or expert(s), assessment of technologies, knowledge syntheses (systematic and scoping reviews), evaluations methods of intervention (ETMI method), workshops and sessions, measures of satisfaction of users

Tools: SWOT analysis, business model canvas, Innovation management standard (CEN/TS 16555 - covered 7 standards, after ISO 56002:2019)

4.4.7 Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study

Description: Concept test is low cost and quick process in which high-level concept(s) is tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews and surveys. In order to conduct concept test, preliminary concept description must exist in written or visual format, which is then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback for the initial concept proposal and its possible variations. Concept test can also include a feasibility study, which also covers technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept. In all, concept-testing phase verifies if a concept has market interest, while feasibility study shows if the product or service based on concept can be developed. Collected feedback includes also improvement suggestions.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Core service in LL

Participants' role: two main actors (projects and companies), joint work among Living Labs and interested partners/stakeholders

Process phase: after concept co-creation

Objectives:

- verifies if a concept has market or research interest,
- testing early “prototypes” to get feedback for development, identify improvement suggestions,
- concept feasibility test focuses on verifying if concept can be technical/economically done (preliminary assessment),
- provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs, identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests, personalized in the client need and varies case by case

Methods: survey, demo-session, interview, wizard of oz

Tools: paper prototype, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), visual VR can be used to test-multitasking (real work), long term evaluations, interviews, questionnaires,

4.4.8 Equipment and facility rental service

Description: Offering equipment, labs, spaces, human resources and other facilities for rent. Some Living Labs do this based on a win-to-win agreement where money does not change hand. Also, some Living Labs require research collaboration when renting.

R&D service categories: Networking and capacity building

Key characteristics in living lab context:

Participants' role: In some cases, researchers can visit the LL and use the provided facilities for free of charge

Objectives:

- Getting temporary human, space, technical or other facility resources,
- Enable research collaboration

Methods: Payment, research collaboration grounded on living lab resources

Tools: Simulation lab

4.4.9 Expert opinion, and advisory services

Description: Expert(s) who have long-standing practical and/or scientific experience in the field of enquiry provide(s) a well-founded written or oral answer for your questions, including the ethics domain/ ethics guidelines, and offer(s) advisory services on the use of specific equipment. Expert(s) are discussing ideas and problems from a different angle to respectfully challenge, test and refine ideas (e.g. as devil’s advocate looking for problems). Qualified and traceable arguments in favor of and against a specific position in an applied issue to support decision-making and development activities. Professional work is a paid service, but “consultation” can be a free of charge service. In most cases it is done by living lab on its own or hosting organization personnel.

R&D service categories: All categories

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Typically consists of one-to-one relationship between the customer and the expert, but may include opinions from multiple experts.

- Internal or external experts (local, national and international experts)
- Multidisciplinary collaboration/Pool of experts

Objectives:

- Offer advice on UX or usability studies,
- consulting care solutions (ICT and devices), in specific/narrow fields in which living lab has experts (e.g., energy consumption calculations),
- consulting on consent and ethics requirement and processes,
- consulting technical solutions (ICT, medical and other devices, sensors, wearables, health apps, machine learning, medical engineering)
- consulting legal issues, networking and contacting people (e.g., doctors, academia, pharmacy, healthcare professionals, policy makers, local ecosystem actors), research ideas,
- innovation management, interventions,
- creation of training materials and processes

Methods: one to one and group discussion, advisory board, expert identification

Tools/Online tools: ethical tools, training materials

4.4.10 Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)

Description: Foresighting is a practice of exploring expected and alternative futures. Trend is a general tendency or direction evident from past events increasing or decreasing in strength of frequency of observation. A weak signal is an indicator of a potentially emerging issue that may become significant in the future. “Wild card” is high-impact event that seem too incredible or is considered too unlikely to happen; yet many do happen.

R&D service categories: Market and competitor intelligence services, Co-creation

Objectives:

- policy consulting,
- create a future vision,
- identify new opportunities and risks,

Methods: back casting, brainstorming, user/citizen panels, workshop/session, expert panel, interview, literature review, role playing, scenarios, survey, SWOT, wild card & weak signals, Science fiction/crazy ideas

4.4.11 Temporary research funding

Description: Providing funding (or an investment) for research, product and business development for small and medium-sized companies or start-ups. Typically, funding is targeted for short-term small-scale experiments or if an externally funded project has resources for this kind of activity (e.g., open calls). Also, can be done in collaboration with local research centers, publicly funded “development companies” and networks or similar.

R&D service categories: Networking and capacity building, project planning and management

Objectives:

- providing funding to execute small scale living lab project (e.g. testing)

Methods: Offering funds within funded projects for small-scale testing or co-creation

4.4.12 Grant writing and funding application support service

Description: Offering tailored support by identifying the proper local, regional, national and international funding instruments, helping to write and manage a funding application process

including finding the right partners for the project if needed. In most cases a living lab will become a project partner but it can also be provided as a paid service without participation.

R&D service categories: Networking and capacity building

Objectives:

- Acquiring/providing funding for “customer” to execute a living lab project or buy living lab services,
- getting project partner for a living lab project

4.4.13 Idea selection and testing

Description: Idea testing is a low-cost and quick process in which high-level ideas are selected (i.e. ranked) or tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews, surveys or during the workshop. In order to conduct idea testing, different high-level ideas are pre-described in written or in visual format, and then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback on the already existing idea proposal. Feedback can also include improvement suggestions.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Objectives:

- Collect feedback, prioritize ideas or different alternative options,
- lowering development risk by selecting best/most promising idea for further development,
- challenge the ideas from different perspectives

Methods: Co-creation workshop, interviews, focus groups, surveys, questionnaires, small group discussions, informal talks

4.4.14 Impact assessment and validation test

Description: Impact assessment is a formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the total outcome that comes as a result of the tested activity, above and beyond what would have happened anyway. Depending on the duration and scope of the validation process impact can be evaluated on individuals, organizations and the society in the short, medium and long term. Validation is the documented act of demonstration that a product or a service will consistently lead to the expected results. Validation test ensures that the product or the service actually meets the defined requirements and demonstrates that the solution fulfils its intended use when deployed on appropriate real environment.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- The validation test is usually designed by LL
- Validation testing has to meet some minimum TRL level in order reliable test the solution impact

Objectives:

- Verify that the develop solution will consistently lead to the expected results and meet defined requirement,
- evaluate social impact,
- quantify change after solution usage

Methods: Survey, observation, pre and post measurement (short and long term), quantitative measures (e.g., physiological measures), feasibility study, usability study, interviews

Tools/online tools: questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors, thermal cameras

4.4.15 Innovation network orchestration

Description: Establishing productive working relationship between existing and previously unconnected but complementary actor parties and helping them (companies, public health and other sector, academia, and end-user stakeholders) to work together properly and well. Handling conflicts and supporting interactions.

R&D service categories: Networking and capacity building

Objectives:

- establish new collaboration relationships,
- promote living lab methodology and raising awareness,
- lobbying living lab movement

Methods: events, seminars, webinars, conferences, one-to-one meetings, site visits, publications (scientific and professional), memberships in local/regional/national/international associations/networks

4.4.16 Large-scale real-life testing and piloting

Description: Similar to small-scale testing but with a longer duration or larger number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group. During piloting, the aim is to evaluate the full scale and near or fully functional product(s) or service(s) at the system level in real environment with real end-users to make sure that the solution is scalable. Includes often impact assessment and validation testing.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Usually, the aim of the testing defines the number of participants
- Sometimes, for large numbers the LL can hire a specialized company for support

Objectives:

- Evaluate scalability,
- evaluate system level impact and functionality,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, longitudinal study, sensors, interview, survey, observation, ethnographic studies, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

4.4.17 Legal, regulation and safety standard support

Description: Providing support to navigate to the legal, regulatory and safety standard requirements and help planning to meet the requirements.

R&D service categories: All categories

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Legal design and decision-making support
- Support on signed agreements, protocol
- In some cases, external contractors for IPR, RGDPDR

Objectives:

- Similar to expert opinion and advisory services but focusing on legal and regulatory issues

4.4.18 Living lab project planning and management

Description: Planning project goals, costs, schedule, list of deliverables, delivery dates and resources. Written project plan for one or multiple innovation stages is made. In the project management, planned tasks are completed by executing, monitoring, controlling, and closing the work of a project team to achieve specific goals and to meet specific success criteria at the specified time.

R&D service categories: Project planning and management

Objectives:

- successful development and implementation of all project procedures,
- supervision and quality control,
- internal/external communication,
- optimization of the allocated resources,
- getting clients and funding,

Tools: Project management guidelines, teams, excel, email, phone, messaging application,

4.4.19 Marketing and sales support

Description: Providing marketing and sales support for 1) making right contacts by giving business contacts, sales and business leads, 2) setting up and arranging meetings and events, 3) showcasing products and services in a showroom or giving online/onsite visibility in living lab own communication channels, 4) providing “user approved” certification, and 5) offering soft landing support to help to setup business in given living lab country or region.

R&D service categories: Marketing and sales support, networking and capacity building

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- It can be introductory to healthcare companies and service providers and goes up to the point of developing a BM

Objectives:

- Finding right contacts and customers for living lab clients,

Tools: “user approved” certification, showroom, showcasing, business meetings, interviews, events, soft landing services, sales/business leads

4.4.20 Panel management

Description: Panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g. patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have given their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up.

R&D service categories: Project planning and management, networking and capacity building

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Group of patients, students but also experts/experts by experience and other staff can also be used as a panel (needs to agreed case by case)
- Having engagement procedures in place (win to win situation), social activities

Objectives:

- enable fast participant recruitment,
- lower the management effort (no need to fill profile information multiple times)

Method: survey, recruitment collaboration with medical professionals (e.g., in hospital ward)

Tools: intake questionnaire, phone, open calls in social media/web, posters, email, personal invitations

4.4.21 Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing

Description: Post-market surveillance is a “real world” test of medical innovations in patient subgroups. It is a practice of monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market. Market acceptance testing focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation, Market and competitor intelligence services

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Usually within a clinical or community research context (within the context of specific projects/the products that come out as research outcomes) and not as a standalone service.
- As normal customer feedback collection and health promotion, for continuum improvement of the tool

Objectives:

- monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market,
- evaluate social impact,
- identify new opportunities for business and research

Methods: survey, observation, interviews, helpdesk logs, technical logs, complain reports, pre and post measurement (long term), market studies

Tools/online tools: questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors

4.4.22 Prototyping test

Description: Prototyping test is a low cost and quick process in which product or service with limited functionality and interaction is tested with real end-users. Interactive prototype product or service must exist so real end-users or experts can experience it. Prototype can be, for instance,, an interactive mock-up of a web service, which interface looks like a real thing. One can navigate through different screens and see simulated content. Also, the service prototype can consist of role-playing exercise to simulate service encounters. The main aim is to collect feedback on as real kind of user experience as possible, but at a lower cost. Different methods such as interviews, surveys and observations can be used.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- From rapid prototyping to the MVP
- IT solutions/Physical and cognitive exercises

Objectives:

- similar to proof-of-concept but testing higher fidelity solution,
- identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: survey, observation, demo-session, interview, wizard of oz, usability tests, role playing

Tools: paper prototype, wireframes, interactive mockups, scaled down prototypes, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), video recording, usability questionnaires, eye tracking

4.4.23 Public procurement support services

Description: Public procurement (e.g., related to research activities) is governed by EU and national rules. Support with public contract issues and the public procurement process is given to help clients to meet the tendering criteria and/or join the tendering process. Also helping public authorities to establish market dialogue when developing the public procurement announcement. This includes Pre-Commercial Procurement and innovative procurement processes.

R&D service categories: Networking and capacity building, co-creation, advisory services, marketing and sales support

Key characteristics in living lab context:

- Pre-commercial procurement, innovative procurement, public procurement
- Project based
- Validation Software (integration) - Hardware (operational validation in real environment)
- Legal design and decision-making support

Methods: Planning process based on co-creation, pre-commercial procurement (PCP), innovative procurement

4.4.24 Simulation test

Description: Simulation is a technique that creates a situation and environment, which allows end-users to experience a representation of a real event in a risk-free environment. Predefined simulation scenario defines a particular set of conditions to resemble authentic situations in a location where a simulation experience takes place to test and to gain understanding of tested solution and related human interactions. After simulation event, facilitators and end-users re-examine the simulation experience, and various aspects of the completed simulation are discussed.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in living lab context

- Mainly for ICT solutions
- Simulation labs, smart home that simulate real-life home/specific scenarios to simulate real space

Objectives:

- simulate real-life situations and behavior but lower cost,
- identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Simulation test, virtual reality (VR), usage scenarios, interview, debriefing, observation, survey, wizard of oz, sensors, usage logs, hospital ward, interactive patient mannequin, usage scenarios,

Tools: audio recording, video recording

4.4.25 Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation

Description: An experiment is a small-scale and short-term preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility of the suggested product or service and to improve it based on the testing result. Testing includes a small number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in living lab context

- Usually lab-based studies
- Can mostly involve qualitative feedback
- Testing quality and user satisfaction,

Objectives:

- verify that the develop solution will work also in real-life setting,
- evaluate usability before engaging more people in testing,

Methods: testing in real-life setting with real users, survey, sensors, interview, survey, observation, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

Tools: validate questionnaires

4.4.26 Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping

Description: Identifying groups, organizations, and people who are relevant stakeholders. Prioritizing and ranking stakeholders based on their perspectives and interest. Mapping the relationship between different stakeholders and company objectives. Deliverable(s) Written report.

R&D service categories: Networking and capacity building, Market and competitor intelligence services, co-creation

Key characteristics in living lab context

- Within a research context / for programs and projects.
- Trying to promote a diversity-centered design

Pre-tasks: Searching and listing all the interested stakeholders/partners, contacting them, and then mapping possible contributors

Objectives:

- identifying relevant/key/negative stakeholders,
- identify stakeholders' interest,
- provide information to participant recruitment

Methods: focus group, workshop, interviews, questionnaires methodology, social network analysis, two-dimensional matrix (e.g., power, influence, interest/need, support/attitude), primary/secondary/tertiary stakeholder, the salience model

Tools: Miro online whiteboard, user requirement analysis

4.4.27 Usability testing

Description: Usability testing is a technique used to evaluate a product by testing it in order to give direct input on how real users use or would use the product or service. Usability inspection is conducted when a professional evaluator inspects a user interface and gives an expert opinion regarding the usability. This approach does not involve real user. Usability testing with real users includes real users who have no prior exposure to the product or service. In the context of Living Labs is mostly provided real user testing.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation

Objectives: Identify usability problems, provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,

Methods: Moderated/unmoderated, remote/in-person, comparative testing, open ended explorative testing, user satisfaction, phone/video interview, usability lab testing, session recordings, observation

Tools: SUS, QUEST, feasibility assessment and other several tests, eye-tracking camera

4.5 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

The following table presents the available technologies for data collection from VITALISE consortium Living Labs. The database will be continuously updated aiming to include the most commonly used technologies but also custom-made solutions from each Living Lab.

Table 9 Devices and technologies provided by Living Labs

Categories	Data collection technology name	Description	To measure
Activity	Balance measure	Ainone Balance® Software is intended for use by health, social and sports professionals to support the assessment of balance and to detect changes in human performance (Class I medical device – MDD 93/42/EEC)	Human balance
Activity	Activity monitoring	Smart wristband watch	Accelerometer, barometer, gyroscope, heart rate sensor, light sensor
Activity	Activity sensor	The ultimate wearable sensor for measuring movement and heart rate in sports and other activities	Movement measurement (9-axis IMU) Heart rate (bpm), R-R intervals, single channel ECG (non-medical), Bluetooth heart rate profile Temperature
Activity	Activity Trackers and wearables	Various wearables to track activity and physiological parameters (Movement, EDA, HR) and analysis to extract activities, postures , stress	Posture, Movement, Activity Level and Stress Level
Activity	Advanced Daily Activity Monitoring Solution	A set of home sensors that can track the presence of a person in different places inside a house, or when the person has left the house. The presence of the person and its movement between rooms in a house. With some feature engineering there are a lot of low and	Home sensor monitoring

		high level features that can be extracted (e.g. sleep duration/pattern/quality, bath visits/duration, guests and socialization, home wondering, walk speed, trend of transition speed, IADLs, Frailty, Depression, IADL decline, Behavioural anomaly)	
Activity	ehcobutler - Book of Life	A modular open environment platform to promote health, satisfaction and personal well-being of elder people with mild cognitive impairments. The platform includes leisure and care activities, such as Book of Life, My Memories, Walking in Relaxing Nature, Cognitive training through GRADIOR, Videoconference, e-mail, Internet, Lifestyle recommendations, Nutritional recommendations...	Well-being, cognitive training
Activity	G-Walk	G-WALK is a small inertial sensor that is used for the study of dysfunctional human movement. It relays 12 spatio-temporal parameters of gait and three planes of pelvic movement to a PC via Bluetooth connection.	Gait, performance
Activity	Inverse kinematics data	A jacket equipped with 6 Adafruit's 9-DOF sensors (3 for each hand), that solves the inverse kinematic problem of 2, 7-DOF hands.	Inverse kinematics data
Activity	motion capture	A sensor suit which enables the collection of precise position and angles of the different body parts . Used to monitor activities, and contrast with other, not so intrusive, technologies	Body Position
Activity	Orientation analysis	BNO055 is a smart 9-DOF sensor that collects data from an accelerometer, a magnetometer and a	Orientation

		gyroscope and does sensor fusion in order to produce the absolute orientation of the chip.	
Activity	Polar team pro	Polar Team Pro combines high-precision GPS-derived movement data , inertial sensor metrics and integrated heart rate monitoring, into a mobile and easy-to-use, wearable player tracking system	Physical activity, physical performance
Activity	Smart Watches	Garmin Vivosmart 4 is a fitness and health monitoring tool which include estimated wrist-based heart rate , all-day stress tracking , relaxation breathing timer , VO2 max , Body Battery energy monitor	heart rate, VO2 max, stress tracking, Body Battery
Activity	Smart Watches	The Wavelet Wristband measures physiological and activity data . The wristband tracks steps, sleep, calories burned, heart rate and blood oxygen saturation. This is a cloud-based, clinical monitoring device is designed for large-scale patient data collection and analysis.	steps, sleep, calories burned, heart rate, blood oxygen
Activity	Wearables	The E4 is a medical-grade wearable device that offers real-time physiological data acquisition , enabling researchers to conduct in-depth analysis and visualization.	physiological and behavioural biomarkers
Environment/context	Air quality sensor	Air quality sensor with WiFi connectivity	Concentration levels PM1, PM2.5 and PM10
Environment/context	Air quality sensor	Air quality sensor with WiFi connectivity	Concentration levels PM2.5 Pressure, Temperature, & Humidity Sensor
Environment/context	Blinds actuator	Blinds are 100% domotic, every time they are actioned can be monitored	Blind operation

Environment/context	Cama-up (behavior patterns, alarms ...)	Device to assist people with reduced mobility in the actions of getting into and out of bed, with monitoring of usage habits and alarm system.	usage habits, alarm system
Environment/context	CAPTAIN - virtual coach for home assistance	Technology developed in the Living Lab for coaching of older adults	
Environment/context	Doors and windows sensors and actuator	magnetic sensor on each window and door, so they can be monitored independently of manual or automatic operation	Door operation window operation
Environment/context	ehcobutler - Book of Life platform for older people	A modular open environment platform to promote health, satisfaction and personal well-being of elder people with mild cognitive impairments. The platform includes leisure and care activities, such as Book of Life, My Memories, Walking in Relaxing Nature, Cognitive training through GRADIOR, Videoconference, e-mail, Internet, Lifestyle recommendations, Nutritional recommendations...	Well-being, cognitive training
Environment/context	Flood sensors	a resistive moisture sensor connected to a generic KNX transceiver	Technical alerts (Flood)
Environment/context	Light level sensor	a KNX connected luminosity sensor for monitoring indoor conditions	Luminosity
Environment/context	Presence Sensor	a KNX connected Passive Infra-Red sensor for monitoring indoor movements	Presence
Environment/context	Sensewear Armband	Energy expenditure measure	Physical activity
Environment/context	Sleep sensors	Various wearable of mattress sensors to assess sleep quality	Sleep Quality
Environment/context	Smart Home Sensors for Activity Recognition	Smart home sensors (Presence, Appliance/Object use etc.) and analysis to recognize activities in time	Activities of Daily Living

		and in turn user behaviors/function/cognitive decline	
Environment/context	Smoke sensors and Fire sensors	Detect smoke and high temperature, above the stove	Technical alerts (smoke, temperature)
Environment/context	Temperature sensor	a KNX connected temperature sensor for indoor temperature monitoring	Temperature
Virtual reality/interactive technology	VR headset	Virtual reality is a fascinating way which let you look around a virtual space as if you're actually there or play a game as though you're really in it.	Virtual reality
Virtual reality/interactive technology	Interactive screens	big touch screens capable of showing and interacting with web pages (e.g., questionnaire response)	Web Interaction
Virtual reality/interactive technology	Emocube3	An interaction prototype used by the user to select a face (representing emotion, or any other metric), as well as gestures	Alternative and augmentative Interaction
Virtual reality/interactive technology	Neurologic	Intervention system to address the decline of executive function through the combination of Virtual Reality and Neurofeedback technologies and Third-Generation Therapies (Mindfulness). The system allows the real-time integration of data from EEG technology in order to identify higher cognitive functions and emotional states that allow adjustments in the activity during the performance. Virtual Reality technologies facilitate that the stimulus, activities or strategies learned have a direct transfer to everyday life environments.	Adjust treatments and therapy. Real-time feedback for patients. Offer structured data to evaluate the cognitive evolution of patients as of their performance in the training sessions.
Virtual reality/interactive technology	AI Emotional Analysis	Digital components for the speech analysis and speech generation to	Speech analysis and intuitive user interface

		provide intuitive user interface	
Cognitive function	Gradior suite	GRADIOR Suite is a neuropsychological intervention suite for a comprehensive approach to the therapy. This comprehensive approach intends to contribute to maintain the cognitive function, control of behavioural symptomatology, improve well-being, quality of life and independence of people with cognitive impairment or deficit. GRADIOR Suite allows to address the cognitive dimension of people through the use of 'GRADIOR Cognitive Stimulation', a support tool oriented to cognitive training and stimulation. GRADIOR Suite also allows to address the sensorial and emotional dimension of people with 'GRADIOR Multisensorial', another support tool, based on Virtual Reality, to work the different senses inducing states of relaxation and sensorial stimulation and, at the same time, working on the behavioural symptomatology.	Adjust treatments and therapy. Offer structured data to evaluate the cognitive evolution of patients as of their performance in the training sessions.
Assisting technology	ANDIN (voice commands, gait patterns)	Smart walker that assists people with mobility difficulties, enhances their autonomy, safety and increases their well-being. helps the person to walk safely, assists their steps, adapts to their speed, detects obstacles, makes emergency calls	usage habits, alarm system, voice commands, walking speed, distance with the user, location
Assisting technology	INOTEC (bathroom shedding patterns)	Smart toilet aimed at people with mobility problems, to enhance their autonomy in a safe way and their well-being. assists the person in getting into and out of the	water temperature, drying temperature, usage habit.

		toilet. User cleaning. toilet cleaning.	
Assisting technology	Robots – Human-Robot interaction	Humanoid robotic head for verbal human-robot interaction	Natural Language Understanding Intent and entity identification Gesture detection (smile) Engaged users Video stream
Assisting technology	Robots – Human-Robot interaction	Social humanoid robot	Speech recognition Human recognition
Assisting technology	Robots – Human-Robot interaction	Social humanoid robot	Speech recognition Human recognition: Engagement state Age Gender Mood Excitement Smile state Attention Intention Pictures Map
Assisting technology	Pepper social robot	The social robot, named Pepper, will serve as a mean to screen, monitor and interact with older adults with cognitive impairment (e.g., MCI, mild dementia) in care facilities. The interaction with Pepper will accompany patients and motivate them to perform activities in order to stimulate cognitive and neuropsychological domains . Also, Pepper will	Capture Cognitive activities performance; capture progress of in different indicators for wellbeing and personalized recommendations; Big data collection.

		provide a mean to big data collection in order to assist the healthcare professional to improve the efficacy of the implemented intervention.	
Biometrics	Biometrics measurement	The Hellenic Educational Self-Care and Support Heart Failure app. An app designed to help patients with heart failure self-report and monitor their status. It integrates blood pressure, Weight, dyspnoea, blood glucose, swellings, bpm, SpO2 Patient's mood and reaction to certain assistive tips	Basic biometrics
Physiological monitoring	blood sugar level	iHealth Gluco is a medical device that designed for diabetic patients, measures blood sugar levels	blood sugar level
Physiological monitoring	Cosmed K5 metabolic system for both laboratory and field testing	COSMED K5, the 4th generation of the most popular wearable metabolic system, a breakthrough in the field of exercise physiology and human performance assessment. The extensive list of new and unique characteristics of the K5 expands the scope of metabolic testing from clinical exercise testing to performance assessment.	Energy expenditure, physical activity etc.
Physiological monitoring	Dynamometer	The Digital Hand Dynamometer is a stand-alone device developed to be used just like a traditional hydraulic hand dynamometer. Highly accurate grip strength measurement from 0-200 pounds (lbs.) or from 0-90 kilograms (kg) are digitally displayed on the LCD, and up 20 test results for each hand can be stored in memory during testing.	dynamometer, digital hand dynamometer

Biosignals	Electroencephalography (EEG)	Electroencephalography (EEG) is an electrophysiological monitoring method to record electrical activity on the human scalp that has been shown to represent the macroscopic activity of the surface layer of the brain underneath. It is typically non-invasive, with the electrodes placed along the scalp. EEG measures voltage fluctuations resulting from ionic current within the neurons of the brain. EEG refers to the recording of the brain's spontaneous electrical activity over a period of time, as recorded from multiple electrodes placed on the scalp.	electrophysiological timeseries
Biosignals	EEG (electroencephalogram), orientation	The EMOTIV EPOC+ is a portable, high resolution, 14-channel, EEG system. It was designed to be quick and easy to fit and take measurements in practical research applications	EEG, orientation
Biosignals	Electronic Medical Recording of Acute Ischemic Episodes	Iliaktis is a digital registry that provides specialized forms for the data gathering of patients with ischemic episodes . It can collect data that refer to the episode itself and also the follow ups of the patient for up to a year in recovery . It gathers data regarding heart disease, Ischemic episode data, CA Report, Discharge data, Follow-up data for 1 month/6months/12months after the episode.	Patient history & demographics

Physiological monitoring	Pulse Oximeter	Pulse oximeter is a device that is placed on a fingertip. It uses light beams to estimate the oxygen saturation of the blood and the pulse rate.	pulse oxygen and pulse rate
Physiological monitoring	Scale	iHealth scale bluetooth can be used to calculate the weight, BMI . iHealth's scales can assist those who are overweight in their battle against obesity.	Weight, BMI

5 Conclusion

This document presents information about the collection of data and analysis towards the creation of the Standard Version 1 for Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain. From the work that has been done so far, the authors concluded that there are various domains that will be benefited from the Harmonization processes and that there is need for Harmonization in various contexts (Section 4.1). The Standard Version 0.1 is a first attempt of defining different concepts in a structured way. The attempt will continue in an iterative way and its results will be released every 6 months. VITALISE consortium envisions to create a methodology that will continue to evolve even after the end of the project and that will be adopted by other thematic areas Living Labs (e.g., urban Living Labs) in order to capture the particularities of each domain but also identify the similarities across Living Lab practices.

6 References

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7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1

The Living Lab self-evaluation designed by Forum LLSA.

DOMAIN	Criterion	Activities vs Results # of item
DIRECTION	1. Purpose, Vision & strategy	x 5
	2. Organisational Culture & Leadership	x 4
EXECUTION	3. Engaging Stakeholders	x5
	4. Creating sustainable Value	x4
	5. Driving Performance & Transformation	x5
RESULTS	6. Stakeholders Perceptions	Open
	7. Strategic & operational Performance	Open

DOMAIN	Criterion	LL & TB
DIRECTION	1. Purpose, Vision & strategy	-Governance of the Living Lab -Strategy & value proposition
	2. Organisational Culture & Leadership	-Monitoring & quality management -Legal & regulatory operational
EXECUTION	3. Engaging Stakeholders	-User & stakeholder involvement -Human resources dimension -Real-life dimension of the living lab
	4. Creating sustainable Value	-Methodology dimension -Financial sustainability
	5. Driving Performance & Transformation	-General operational processes
RESULTS	6. Stakeholders Perceptions	Open
	7. Strategic & operational Performance	Open

A		B	C	D
			Self-assessment framework	<i>Remaining criteria: 0</i>
1				
2	Component	No.	Criteria	How true is the statement
3	Governance	1	The LL's organisation and each individual's roles and duties are clearly identified.	Yes
4		2	Groups, panels or other arrangements are in place to ensure a balance between the various interests.	Probably Yes
5		3	All of the LL's stakeholders (users, researchers, institutions, industrial operators, etc.) are properly represented in project steering committees.	Probably Yes
6	Strategy and policies	4	With the help of its local or regional institutional supports, the LL is included in local and regional initiatives.	Probably Yes
7		5	Changes in public policies (epidemiology, sociology, industry, research) are monitored on a regular basis so as to identify and monitor projects accordingly.	Probably No
8		6	The LL takes all regulatory requirements in the healthcare sector into account (clinical study, marketing authorisation, CE marking, etc.).	Probably Yes
9		7	The LL has a collaboratively-drawn up code of ethics and conduct. Everyone involved in the LL is familiar with this code of ethics and conduct.	Probably Yes
10		8	Everyone involved in the LL is familiar with the EIT Health code of conduct.	Probably No
11		9	A value proposition is developed for each service or intervention which guarantees the user benefits for the solutions supported by the LL as long as the recommendations provided are followed by the leader.	Probably Yes
12		10	The LL has a structured offering that lists and presents the services it can provide.	Probably Yes
13	Human resources	11	The skills and expertise of the LL's employees are appropriate to the LL's core business.	Probably Yes
14		12	The LL's employees are trained in co-design and iterative project management.	Probably Yes
15		13	Design group meetings are conducted by qualified facilitators.	Probably No
16		14	Skills that are not available within the LL itself can be accessed on a long-term basis through its usual partners.	Probably Yes
17		15	The LL has a method for identifying and recruiting users for each project.	Probably No
18				